

BELFAST REGION CITY DEAL

AN ANALYSIS OF NET-ZERO CARBON OPTIONS FOR THE BELFAST REGION

Prof. Andy Gouldson,
Andrew Sudmant and
Ruaidhri Higgins-Lavery

Contents

PREFACE	3
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
Background	4
Baselines and Targets.....	4
Cost-Effective Options.....	4
More Ambitious Options.....	6
Next Steps	7
INTRODUCTION	8
Context.....	8
OUR APPROACH	9
(a). Measuring an Area’s Carbon Footprint	9
(b). Developing a Baseline of Past, Present and Future Emissions.....	9
(c). Setting Science-Based Carbon Reduction Targets.....	10
(d). Identifying and Evaluating Carbon Reduction Opportunities	10
(e). Aggregating Up to See the Bigger Picture	11
(f). Developing Targets and Performance Indicators.....	11
(g). Focusing on Key Sectors.....	11
A BASELINE OF PAST, PRESENT AND FUTURE EMISSIONS FOR THE BELFAST REGION.....	12
SETTING SCIENCE-BASED CARBON REDUCTION TARGETS FOR THE BELFAST REGION	15
AGGREGATING UP: THE BIGGER PICTURE FOR THE BELFAST REGION	16
a) Emissions reductions.....	16
b) The most carbon- and cost-effective options	17
c) Investment needs, paybacks and employment creation.....	18
FOCUSING ON KEY SECTORS IN THE BELFAST REGION	21
(a). Domestic Buildings.....	22
(b). Public & Commercial Buildings	26
(c). Transport.....	30
(d). Industry.....	33
(e): Land Use.....	36
BELFAST REGION’S NET-ZERO EMISSIONS PATHWAY	41
NEXT STEPS FOR THE BELFAST REGION	42
i) Accept the Need for High Levels of Ambition	42
ii) Focus on the Main Priorities.....	42
iii) Take a Joined-Up Approach to Change.....	43
iv) Understand Roles and Share Responsibilities	43
v) Develop a Positive Vision.....	43
vi) Build Legitimacy.....	44
vii) Assess Readiness and Build a Pipeline	44
viii) Explore Business Models and Build Capabilities for Programme Development Some text.....	44
ix) Evaluate and Learn from Progress.....	45
x) Celebrate and Build on Success.....	45
APPENDICES	46
Appendix 1 – Glossary and acronyms.....	46
Appendix 2 – Local authority sectoral baseline emissions, projected emissions and SBTs.....	47
Appendix 3 – Local authority land use breakdowns.....	57
Appendix 4 – Land-use sub-sector mitigation pathways.....	58
Appendix 5– Belfast Region’s league table of most carbon-effective options.....	61
Appendix 6 – Belfast Region’s league table of most cost-effective options.....	71
Appendix 7 – Local authority data sources and case study references.....	81

PREFACE

The Belfast Region City Deal (BRCD) represents a new way of working between central and local government and regional partners and secures a bespoke package of investment from central government and the BRCD partners of more than £850 million to support the delivery of our shared vision of inclusive economic growth. By leveraging additional private sector investment, the partners will deliver a programme with an overall value well over £1 billion, strengthening the region's offer in growth sectors such as life and health sciences, the digital and creative industries, and advanced manufacturing. It will support next generation digital capabilities, boost tourism and support our region's regeneration, underpinned by infrastructure developments and skills investment to connect people to jobs and services.

The BRCD Partners recognise that although we have sought to integrate within our deal, projects that will support the delivery of more sustainable development, with for example planned investments in centres of excellence in the application of digital twin technologies, advanced manufacturing and clean-tech and a net-zero challenge fund, there is much more to be done by all the partners if we are to achieve our statutory net-zero targets and grasp the economic opportunities of being at the forefront of the net-zero transition.

The Partners therefore agreed to commission this report to help provide an evidence base to inform their decisions going forward. This report does not seek to suggest that there is a single pathway for tackling net-zero, rather it outlines the scale of the challenge and the difficult choices that we will face in the coming years. As well as identifying the choices and the considerable cost of achieving net-zero it also outlines the value and economic benefits in terms of jobs that will come from such investments.

Much of the work to tackle net-zero will fall beyond the remit of the BRCD and it will be for partners, working with their communities and alongside industry and government to determine the options that they will prioritise to tackle net-zero. However, the BRCD is a significant partnership and a major investment programme and therefore this report will also inform project sponsors and Deal leaders as we continue to develop our plans for the deal and deliver our investment projects to not only deliver more and better jobs but also strive for growth which is both inclusive and sustainable.

Damien Martin
Programme Director
Belfast Region City Deal

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Background

- i. Scientific evidence calls for rapid reductions in global carbon emissions if we are to limit average levels of warming to 1.5°C and so avoid the risks associated with dangerous or runaway climate change.
- ii. Globally, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) suggests that we will have used up the global carbon budget that gives us a good chance of limiting warming to 1.5°C degrees within a decade. This science underpins calls for the declaration of a climate emergency.
- iii. Dividing the global carbon budget up by population gives the Belfast region a total carbon budget of **48.4** million tonnes from **2023**. Based solely on emissions produced within its boundaries, the Belfast region currently emits c.**8.9** million tonnes of carbon a year, and as such it would use up its carbon budget by **the end of 2028**.
- iv. This assessment does not include its broader carbon footprint – for example relating to longer distance travel or the goods and services that are produced elsewhere but consumed within the region (i.e. its Scope 3 emissions).

Baselines and Targets

- Scope 1 and 2 direct carbon emissions from the Belfast region have fallen by **30%** since 1990. With on-going decarbonisation of grid electricity, and taking into account population and economic growth within the city region, we project that the region’s annual emissions output will have fallen by a total of **50%** in 2050, on 1990 levels.
- If it is to stay within its carbon budget, the Belfast region needs to add to the emissions reductions already achieved to secure **56%** reductions on its 1990 level of emissions by 2025, **80%** by 2030, **91%** by 2035, **96%** by 2040, **98%** by 2045 and **100%** by 2050. In short, the majority of all emissions reductions across the region need to be delivered within the next ten years.
- Without further activity to address its carbon emissions, we project that the Belfast region’s annual emissions will exceed its carbon budget by **5** million tonnes in 2030, and **6** million tonnes per annum by 2050.

Belfast region's baseline and science-based targets

Cost-Effective Options

- To meet these carbon reduction targets, the Belfast region will need to adopt low carbon options that close the gap between its projected emissions in future and net-zero emissions. This can be partially realised through cost-effective options that would more than pay for themselves through the energy cost reductions they would generate whilst generating wide social and environmental benefits in the area.
- More specifically, the analysis shows that the Belfast region could close the gap between its projected emissions in 2050 and net-zero emissions by 15% purely through the adoption of cost-effective options in houses, public and commercial buildings, transport and industry.
- Adopting these options would reduce the region’s total projected energy bill in 2050 by £431 million per year whilst also creating 11,629 years of employment in the region. They could also help to generate wider benefits, including helping to tackle fuel poverty, reducing congestion and productivity losses, improving air quality, and enhancements to public health.
- The most carbon-effective options for the region to deliver these carbon cuts include improved deep retrofitting of heating, lighting and insulation in houses, cooling and insulation in offices, shops and restaurants, and a range of measures across the transport sector including modal shift to non-motorised transport and the wider up-take of electric vehicles.

Belfast region's emissions baseline with cost-effective, cost-neutral and technical potential scenarios

More Ambitious Options

- The analysis also shows that the Belfast region could close the gap to net-zero emissions in 2050 (across the buildings, transport, and industrial sectors)¹ by 68% through the adoption of options that are already available, but that some of these options would not pay for themselves directly through the energy savings that they would generate. Many of these options would, however, create wider indirect benefits both economically and socially in the region.
- This means that although it can achieve significant reductions in emissions by focusing on established cost-effective and technically viable measures, the Belfast region still has to identify other more innovative interventions that could deliver the last 32% of shortfall between projected emissions in 2050 and a net-zero target in these sectors.
- Options identified elsewhere that could be considered in the Belfast region include promoting the use of low carbon vehicles, electrification of heating and cooking, and planting trees. Carbon emissions could be cut further still through behavioural and consumption-based changes such as the promotion of active travel (e.g. walking and cycling), reductions in meat and dairy consumption and the generation of food waste, and reduced consumption of concrete and steel with more emphasis on green infrastructure.
- The scale of activity and investment needed to reach or even get close to the carbon emissions reduction targets set is significant. We find that across the region, many hundreds of thousands of homes and square-metres of floorspace will require retrofitting and widespread changes will be needed in the travel patterns and the way that people travel.

Belfast region's remaining sectoral emissions and net-emissions pathway to net-zero by 2050

¹ The land-use sector is the only sector capable of achieving negative emissions using currently available low-carbon measures (ie removing more carbon than it emits), through reductions in livestock numbers and afforestation. Mitigation from the land-use sector has been included in aggregated results, but its inclusion in the above metric would mask the abatement potential of the other sectors.

Next Steps

- The Belfast region needs clear and ambitious climate action plans. The case for such plans is supported by the evidence that much – but not all – of the action that is required can be based on the exploitation of win-win low-carbon options that will simultaneously improve economic, social and health outcomes across the region.
- The Belfast region and other City and Growth Deals should engage with relevant NI Government Departments to consider the most appropriate models for climate action planning and delivery.
- The plans for the Belfast region need to be developed in the context of the agreed approach for Northern Ireland. The recent Climate Change Act should be celebrated as an important step forward for Northern Ireland’s climate-action journey, while recognising that more ambitious, specific and locally-led action is also necessary.
- The Belfast region comprises 60% of Northern Ireland’s population, is responsible for 42% of all territorial emissions, and 33% of the land area and there is therefore a responsibility for partners to advocate for and lead the way in enacting climate action in NI. In order to match emissions reductions and legislative progress in other areas of the UK, as well as the Republic of Ireland, urgent and ambitious action is required across all sectors.
- The climate action plans should adopt science-based targets for emissions reduction. As well as longer term targets, it should include five-yearly carbon reduction targets.
- The action plans should focus initially on the region’s direct (Scope 1 and 2) carbon footprint as these emissions are most directly under the region’s influence, but in time it should also widen its scope to consider its broader (Scope 3) carbon footprint.
- The action plans should also set out the ways in which the Belfast region will work towards achieving these science-based targets, drawing on the deployment Key Performance Indicators listed in this report. Action should also be taken to monitor and report progress on emissions reductions.
- It is important to stress that delivering on these targets will require action across the region and the active support of the public, private and third sectors. Establishing an independent Climate Commission has proven invaluable in Belfast and in other areas, such as Yorkshire and the Humber in England. These commissions help to draw actors together and to build capacities to take and track action.
- Leadership groups should be formed for key sectors such as homes, public and commercial buildings, transport and industry, to develop clear plans for the delivery of priority actions in each sector. All large organisations and businesses in the region should also be asked to match broader carbon reduction commitments and to report back on progress.

INTRODUCTION

Context

Climate science has proven the connection between the concentration of greenhouse gases in the atmosphere and the extent to which the atmosphere traps heat and so leads to global warming. The science tells us – with a very high level of confidence – that such warming will lead to increasingly severe disruption to our weather patterns and water and food systems, and to ecosystems and biodiversity. Perhaps most worryingly, the science predicts that there may be a point where this process becomes self-fuelling, for example where warming leads to the thawing of permafrost in such a way that significant quantities of greenhouse gases are released, leading to further warming. Beyond this point or threshold, the evidence suggests that we may lose control of our future climate and become subject to what has been referred to as dangerous or “runaway” climate change.

Until recently, scientists had determined that this threshold existed at around 2°C of global warming, measured as a global average of surface temperatures. However, more recent scientific assessments (especially by the IPCC in 2018) have suggested that the threshold should instead be set at 1.5°C. This change in the suggested threshold from 2°C to 1.5°C has led to calls for targets for decarbonisation to be made both stricter (e.g. for the UK to move from an 80% decarbonisation target to a net-zero target, which it did in 2019), and to be brought forward (e.g. from 2050 to 2030, which the UK has not done, although many local authorities and other places have set themselves this ambitious goal).

Globally, the IPCC concludes that from 2023 we can only emit 392 billion tonnes of CO₂ if we want to give ourselves a 50% chance of avoiding dangerous climate change. Combined emissions from all countries are currently greater than 36 billion tonnes of CO₂ every year, and we are on track to use up our global carbon budget within a decade. It is this realisation – and the ever accumulating science on the scale of the impacts of climate change – that led to calls for organisations and areas to declare a climate emergency and to develop and implement plans to rapidly reduce carbon emissions.

The University of Leeds has previously published a climate action roadmap for the city of Belfast, highlighting the need for ambitious decarbonisation interventions. This study builds on and extends our previous analysis to include the local authorities of Antrim and Newtownabbey Borough, Ards and North Down Borough, Lisburn & Castlereagh City, Mid and East Antrim Borough and Newry, Mourne and Down District – as well as updating the analysis for the city of Belfast. We have updated our analysis to include baseline emissions analysis and mitigation potential for the Land-Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) and Agriculture sectors. These sectors will be presented under the ‘Land-Use’ sector throughout this report.

This report focusses on mitigation at the Belfast region level, with appendices outlining the breakdowns for each partner local authority. However, while ambitious interventions are often more effective at the local level, the scaling-up of the partner local authorities to the Belfast region and/or Northern Ireland level offers greater opportunities in terms of impact on energy use, emissions and political momentum. Organising and maintaining clear directives and communication between each local authority – while focussing on both local and regional climate action – is key to effective action.

OUR APPROACH

(a). Measuring an Area's Carbon Footprint

Any area's carbon footprint – measured in terms of the total impact of all of its greenhouse gas emissions – can be divided into three types of greenhouse gas emissions.

- Those coming from the fuel (e.g. petrol, diesel or gas) that is directly used within an area and from other sources such as landfill sites or industry within the area. These are known as Scope 1 emissions.
- Those coming from the electricity that is used within the area, even if it is generated somewhere else. These are known as Scope 2 emissions. Together Scope 1 and 2 emissions are sometimes referred to as “territorial” emissions.
- Those associated with the goods and services that are produced elsewhere but imported and consumed within the area. After taking into account the carbon footprint of any goods and services produced in the area but that are exported and consumed elsewhere, these are known as Scope 3 or consumption-based emissions.

In this report we focus on Scope 1 and 2 emissions, and exclude consideration of long-distance travel and of Scope 3 or consumption-based emissions. We do this because Scope 1 and 2 emissions are more directly under the control of actors within an area, and because the carbon accounting and management options for these emissions are better developed. We stress though that emissions from longer distance travel (especially aviation) and consumption are very significant, and also need to be addressed.

(b). Developing a Baseline of Past, Present and Future Emissions

Having a baseline of carbon emissions is key to tracking progress over time. We use local authority emissions data to chart changes in emissions from 2005 to 2020, and historic data back to 1990. We also break this down to show the share of emissions that can be attributed to households, public and commercial buildings, transport and industry.

We then project current emissions levels for the period through to 2050. To do this, we assume on-going decarbonisation of electricity in line with government commitments and a continuation of background trends in a) economic and population growth, and b) energy use and energy efficiency. Specific numbers for the key variables taken into account in the forecasts are presented in the technical annexes attached. As with all forecasts, the level of uncertainty attached increases as the time period in question extends. Even so, it is useful to look into the future to gauge the scale of the challenge to be addressed in each area, especially as it relates to the projected gap between the forecasted emissions levels and those that are required if an area's emissions are to be consistent with a global strategy to limit average warming to 1.5°C.

(c). Setting Science-Based Carbon Reduction Targets

To set science-based carbon reduction targets for an area, we take the total global level of emissions that the IPCC suggests gives us a **50%** chance of limiting average levels of warming to 1.5°C, and divide it according to the share of the global population living in the area in question. This enables us to set the total carbon budget for an area that is consistent with a global budget. To set targets for carbon reduction, we then calculate the annual percentage reductions from the current level that are required to enable an area to stay within its overall carbon budget.

(d). Identifying and Evaluating Carbon Reduction Opportunities

Our analysis then includes assessment of the potential contribution of approximately 750 energy saving or low carbon measures for:

- Households and for both public and commercial buildings (including better insulation, improved heating, more efficient appliances, some small scale renewables)
- Transport (including more walking and cycling, enhanced public transport, electric and more fuel efficient vehicles)
- Industry (including better lighting, improved process efficiencies and a wide range of other energy efficiency measures).

We stress that the list of options that is assessed may not be exhaustive; other options could be available and the list can potentially be expanded.

For the options included, we assess the costs of their purchase, installation and maintenance, the direct benefits (through energy and fuel savings) of their adoption in different settings and their viable lifetimes. We also consider the scope for, and potential rates of deployment of each option. This allows us to generate league tables of the most carbon and cost-effective options that could be deployed within an area.

It is important to note that we base the analysis on current capital costs, although future costs and benefits are adjusted for inflation and discounting factors. This could be overly cautious if costs fall and benefits increase as some options become more widely adopted, or if the costs increase as the rates of deployment increase. It is also important to note that, although we consider the employment generation potential of different options, we do not consider the wider indirect impacts of the different options relating to their social, economic or environmental implications.

(e). Aggregating Up to See the Bigger Picture

Based on this bottom up analysis of the potential for different options to be adopted within the area, we then aggregate up to assess the potential for decarbonisation within that area, and the costs and benefits of different levels of decarbonisation. We then merge the aggregated analysis of the scope for decarbonisation with the baseline projections of future emissions to highlight the extent to which the gap between the projected and required emissions levels that can be met through different levels and forms of action.

To break this gap down, we merge interventions into three broader groupings:

- **Cost-Effective (CE)** options where the direct costs of adoption are outweighed by the direct benefits that they generate through the energy savings they secure, meaning the portfolio of measures as a whole has a positive economic impact in present value. These options may also generate indirect benefits, for example through job creation, fuel poverty and improved air quality and public health.
- **Cost-Neutral (CN)** options where the portfolio of interventions mentioned above is expanded to consider investments that may not be as cost effective on their own terms, but where the range of measures as a whole will have near-zero net cost.
- **Technical Potential (TP)** options where the direct costs are not (at present) covered by the direct benefits. However, the cost of many low carbon options is falling quickly, and again these options could generate important indirect benefits such as those listed above.

(f). Developing Targets and Performance Indicators

Linked to the analysis detailed above, we extend our evaluation of potential emissions reductions across the Belfast region's economy to substantive, real-life indicators for the levels of investment and deployment required to achieve targets. These Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) illustrate the scale of ambition required to reach the emissions savings presented in the Technical Potential scenario and are disaggregated by sector.

(g). Focusing on Key Sectors

As well as presenting an aggregated picture, we also focus on the emissions saving potential in the housing, public and commercial buildings, transport, industry and land-use sectors. We focus on overall investment needs and returns, and present more detailed league tables of the most carbon- and cost-effective options that could be adopted in each sector.

A BASELINE OF PAST, PRESENT AND FUTURE EMISSIONS FOR THE BELFAST REGION

Analysis shows that the Belfast region’s baseline (Scope 1 and 2) emissions have fallen by **30%** since 1990, due to a combination of increasingly decarbonised electricity supply, structural change in the economy, and the gradual adoption of more efficient buildings, vehicles and businesses.

Using projections of the NI electrical grid intensity approaching full decarbonisation by 2050², and taking into account economic growth (assumed at 1.5% p.a.), population growth and on-going improvements in energy and fuel efficiency, we project that the region’s baseline (Scope 1 and 2) emissions will only fall by a further **11%** by 2030, **17%** by 2040, and **20%** by 2050. This is a total of just under **50%** between 1990 and 2050.

Figure 1 – Belfast region's Scope 1 and 2 historic and projected sectoral emissions

Currently, **21%** of the Belfast region’s emissions come from the domestic buildings sector, with transport responsible for **20%** of emissions, public and commercial buildings for **7%** and industry **22%**. Emissions related to land use are marginally the most significant, contributing **24%** (including animal agriculture and cropland). Emissions from the waste sector represent **6%**. By 2050, under a ‘Business as Usual’ scenario (BAU), we predict that emissions from

² <https://www.theccc.org.uk/publication/advice-report-the-path-to-a-net-zero-northern-ireland/>

transport will decrease significantly to **5%** while the share of emissions from domestic buildings increase to **28%**. Land-use emissions are projected to increase proportionally to represent **32%** of all territorial emissions. The emissions share from commercial and public buildings are expected to increase slightly to **8%**, with the share of industrial and waste emissions falling marginally.

Figure 3 - Belfast region's current and projected emissions share by sector

Figure 2 - Belfast region's historic and projected per capita emissions by local authority

Related to this emissions baseline, after evaluating the range of energy sources that the Belfast region consumes (spanning electricity, gas, all solid and liquid fuels across sectors) we find that in 2021, £2.38 billion was spent on energy across the region. Domestic buildings generated the majority of this demand (43%), followed by transport fuels (30%) then industry, public and commercial buildings and agriculture (18%, 6% and 3% respectively). By projecting demand and energy prices into future with reasonable baseline assumptions over population, inflationary measures and efficiency gains across the economy, we find that the Belfast region’s BAU energy expenditure will likely increase to just over £2.43 billion per year in 2030 and c.£2.97 billion per year in 2050, with domestic buildings’ share of expenditure growing significantly 60% in the region’s total (see Figure 4 below). Current prices reflect ongoing turbulence in the energy markets, which are subject to change in the future.

Figure 4 - Belfast region's historic and projected energy expenditure by sector

SETTING SCIENCE-BASED CARBON REDUCTION TARGETS FOR THE BELFAST REGION

The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has shown that from **2023** keeping within a global carbon budget of **392** gigatonnes (i.e. **392** billion tonnes) of CO₂ emissions would give us a **50%** chance of limiting average warming to 1.5°C and therefore avoiding dangerous levels of climate change. If we divide this global figure up on an equal basis by population, and adjust the budget to consider other gases that contribute to climate change, this gives the Belfast region a total carbon budget of c.**48.4** million tonnes over the period between the present and 2050.

At current rates of emissions output, the Belfast region would use up this budget in just under **6** years (at some point during the winter of **2028**). However, the region could stay within its carbon budget by reducing its emissions by c.**15%** year on year. This would mean that transitioning from the current position where emissions are **30%** lower than 1990 levels to a local pathway that is consistent with the world giving itself a 50% chance of avoiding dangerous, runaway climate change, the Belfast region should adopt the following carbon reduction targets (on 1990 levels):

- **56%** reduction by 2025
- **80%** reduction by 2030
- **91%** reduction by 2035
- **96%** reduction by 2040
- **98%** reduction by 2045
- **100%** reduction by 2050

Figure 5 - Belfast region's baseline and science-based targets

AGGREGATING UP: THE BIGGER PICTURE FOR THE BELFAST REGION

a) Emissions reductions

Our analysis predicts that the gap between the Belfast region’s BAU emissions in 2050 and the net-zero target (excluding the land-use sector) could be closed by **15% (976 kt CO₂e)** through the adoption of Cost-Effective (CE) options, by a further **7% (427 kt CO₂e)** through the adoption of additional Cost-Neutral (CN) options at no net cost, and then by an additional **46% (1,544 kt CO₂e)** through the further adoption of all technically viable (TP) options.

Incorporating the land-use sector into these mitigation results provides an opportunity to offset remaining emissions from the domestic buildings, waste, commercial, industrial and transport sectors. Following the UK Climate Change Committee’s (CCC) highest ambition scenario for the land-use sector of a 50% reduction in meat and dairy consumption³, the land-use sector across the Belfast region can be turned from a major carbon source to a significant carbon sink. Updated analysis (March, 2023⁴) shows the CCC’s high ambition scenario suggesting a 50% reduction in livestock numbers for Northern Ireland specifically. Including this mitigation into the TP pathway yields annual sequestration of **458 kt CO₂e** per annum by 2050, or an overall reduction in emissions of **107%**.

Figure 6 - Belfast region's emissions baseline with cost-effective, cost-neutral and technical potential scenarios

³ The CCC presents 5 economy-wide scenarios for achieving the UK’s climate targets. Within these, 3 of the 5 specify a 50% reduction in meat and dairy consumption by 2050.

⁴ <https://www.theccc.org.uk/publication/advice-report-the-path-to-a-net-zero-northern-ireland/>

b) The most carbon- and cost-effective options

Figure 7 presents the emissions savings that could be achieved through different groups of measures in the Belfast region. Appendices 5 and 6 present league tables of specific measures and their potential emissions savings over this period.

Table 1 - Belfast region's potential 5 year emissions reduction percentages

		2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Reduction on BAU Baseline	CE	3%	10%	16%	17%	16%	15%
	CN	4%	13%	21%	23%	22%	22%
	TP	10%	29%	58%	94%	104%	107%
Reduction on 2021 Emissions	CE	3%	10%	13%	13%	12%	11%
	CN	3%	13%	17%	17%	16%	16%
	TP	9%	28%	46%	72%	77%	77%

Figure 7 – Belfast region’s highest emissions reduction measures (top 45). Afforestation of agricultural land removes c45,000 ktCO₂.

Table 2 - Belfast region's top 10 most carbon effective mitigation options

Rank	Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Absolute Emissions Reduction (ktCO ₂ e):	Cost per tonne (£)
1	Land-use	Afforestation of grazing land	45480	14
2	Domestic	Oil boilers to heat pumps in domestic buildings	9378	144
3	Domestic	Whole house retrofits in domestic buildings	5778	488
4	Land-use	Wetlands - High ambition restoration	3556	24
5	Land-use	Reduce urban encroachment on natural areas	3532	-
6	Industry	Condensing and insulation measures to boilers and steam piping in industry	2870	339
7	Land-use	Wetlands - Medium ambition restoration	2651	19
8	Transport	Diesel light ordinary goods vehicle to electric ordinary goods vehicle	2351	-8
9	Land-use	Miscanthus planting	2215	13
10	Transport	Diesel heavy ordinary goods vehicle to electric ordinary goods vehicle	2140	-2

Some of the ideas for innovative options identified elsewhere, that could also be considered for the Belfast region, include targeting a full transition to net-zero homes and public/commercial buildings for new construction by 2030, promoting the rapid acceleration of active travel (e.g. walking and cycling), tackling food waste, reducing meat and dairy consumption and reducing concrete and steel consumption/promoting adoption of green infrastructure.

c) Investment needs, paybacks and employment creation

Exploiting the cost-effective options in households, public and commercial buildings, transport, industry and waste would be economically beneficial. Although such measures would require total investments of around **£3.5** billion over their lifetimes (equating to investments of **£345m** a year across all organisations and households in the region for the next decade), once adopted they would reduce the Belfast region's total energy bill by **£431** million p.a. in 2050 whilst also creating **11,629** years of employment.

By expanding the portfolio of measures at no net cost to the Belfast region's economy (the Cost-Neutral scenario), investments of **£8.8** billion over their lifetimes (or **£883m** a year for the next decade) would generate **26,421** years of employment whilst reducing the region's emissions by **21%** of projected 2050 levels.

Exploiting all technically viable options would be more expensive (at least at current prices, c.**£30** billion or **£3** billion annually for the next decade) but realise further emissions savings – eliminating **78%** of the projected shortfall in the region's 2050 emissions, whilst saving **£1.3** billion from leaving the local economy in energy bills on an annual basis by 2050. It would also create **88,638** years of employment in the area.

Table 3 - Belfast region's five year investments and energy expenditure savings

		2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Cumulative Investment (£, millions)	CE	686	2,433	3,143	3,401	3,451	3,453
	CN	1,546	7,115	8,380	8,758	8,834	8,834
	TP	5,641	25,056	29,921	31,422	31,983	32,310
Annual Energy Expenditure Savings (£, millions)	CE	142	351	380	389	408	431
	CN	183	461	512	543	571	600
	TP	331	875	1,006	1,107	1,200	1,293

Table 4 - Potential investments by sector and scenario

Sector	Scenario	Investment (£, millions)
Domestic	CE	761
	CN	4,469
	TP	16,076
Public and Commercial	CE	969
	CN	1,510
	TP	4,674
Industry	CE	1,504
	CN	2,853
	TP	9,306
Transport	CE	220
	CN	318
	TP	318
Land-Use	CE	0
	CN	2
	TP	1936

Table 5 - Potential job creation by sector and scenario

		Total	Domestic	Industry	Transport	Public and Commercial
Years of employment	CE	11,629	1,627	5,145	301	4,557
	CN	26,421	9,557	9,762	436	7,103
	TP	88,638	34,376	31,838	436	21,989
20-year jobs	CE	581	81	257	15	228
	CN	1,321	478	488	22	355
	TP	4,432	1,719	1,592	22	1,099

To give an indication of the levels of activity required to deliver on these broader targets, the tables below detail total deployment across different sectors in the Belfast region through to 2050. We also give an indication of the rate of deployment required in the region if it is to come close to its climate targets. These lists are not exhaustive, and also apply by measure; any one building or industrial facility will usually require the application of several measures over the period. These figures effectively become Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for the delivery of climate action across the region.

Table 6 - Belfast region's emissions reduction KPIs for domestic buildings

Measure	Total Number of Homes	Annual rate of installations
Lighting Upgrades	366,449	13,087
Floor Insulation	96,242	3,437
Gas Boiler Upgrades & Repairs	136,540	4,876
Glazing Upgrades	62,903	2,247
Solar thermal	48,687	1,739
Solar PV	356,051	12,716
Thermostats & Heating Controls	26,302	939
Loft insulation	200,466	7,160
Wall Insulation	61,816	2,208
Draught Proofing	29,813	1,065
Cavity wall Insulation	108,430	3,872
Heat Pumps	259,554	9,270

Table 7 - Belfast region's emissions reduction KPIs for public and commercial buildings

Low Carbon Measure	Floorspace Applied (m ²)	Annual rate of installation (m ²)
Lighting/heating controls and sensors	2,040,802	72,886
Glazing upgrades	109,977	3,928
Solar thermal	655,396	23,407
Office lighting upgrades	890,804	31,814
Retrofits	1,007,687	35,989
Heat pumps	1,427,045	50,966

Table 8 - Belfast region's emissions reduction KPIs for the transport sector

Measure	Annual target
Car trips shifted to cycling (millions)	5.6
Car trips shifted to walking (millions)	5.6
Electric vehicles purchased	6489
Electric buses purchased	55

FOCUSING ON KEY SECTORS IN THE BELFAST REGION

At full deployment (technical potential scenario) across the Belfast region, we calculate that there is potential to mitigate **122 MtCO₂e** in emissions that will otherwise be produced in the region between 2023 and 2050. The land-use sector will contribute most significantly toward this total, with a decarbonisation potential **62 Mt** of CO₂e in the most ambitious scenario. The domestic sector also has a huge level of decarbonisation potential of **26 MtCO₂e** (technical potential scenario) through the period.

However, transport, industry and public and commercial buildings also play a major role; the full deployment of low-carbon measures in the industrial sector can potentially mitigate **18 Mt**, with transport interventions providing up to **10 Mt** of mitigation from 2022-2050. Upgrading and retrofitting the Belfast region's non-domestic built environment (including public and commercial sectors) could reduce emissions by up to **6 MtCO₂e** over the same period at full technical potential.

Figure 8 - Belfast region's emissions reductions potential by sector and scenarios

Figure 9 - Belfast region's potential emissions reductions share by sector

In the following section, summaries of the emissions reduction potential and economic implications of investment are presented for the five main sectors. For display and continuity purposes, each sector is displayed with a summary of the same metrics: (1) emissions reduction potential over time in the three economic scenarios, (2) five-year totals for cumulative emissions savings, investment requirements and annual energy expenditure reductions, and (3) a simplified table of the most cost-effective low carbon measures applied in each sector across the Belfast region. Low-carbon interventions in the land-use sector - while very carbon-effective - are rarely cost-effective. Therefore scenarios of low, medium and high ambitions have been used in the place of economic scenarios in this section. Throughout the analysis, cost-effective and neutral scenarios for land-use have been used in keeping with other sectors.

(a). Domestic Buildings

The Belfast region represents a significant portion of Northern Ireland's urban landscape, with approximately 494,500 homes and a population of 1.1 million. These houses are primarily detached or bungalows (30%), terraces (30%) and semi-detached (26%). Purpose-built flats account for 12% and converted flats form the remaining 2%.

Homes in the Belfast region are significantly more carbon-intensive in comparison with other areas of the UK. On an average per-house basis, emissions are 3.7 t CO₂e per annum across the Belfast region, in contrast to an average of 2.7 t CO₂e across the UK. This is partly explained by the prevalence of oil heating in Northern Ireland, with 68% of homes relying on central heating through oil boilers. For comparison, only 5% of homes in England rely on oil-fuelled central heating systems. This dependence on carbon-intensive heating presents an economical hurdle for the Belfast region to overcome, as switching from oil boilers to more carbon-friendly technologies, such as ground-source and air-source heat pumps, can be costly. However, it also represents an opportunity to rapidly decarbonise the domestic building stock, as each intervention will be significantly more impactful in terms of carbon mitigation than in other areas of the UK.

As well as heating upgrades, significant improvements in energy efficiency can be gained through the wide-scale promotion and uptake of whole-house retrofits. These deep retrofits significantly reduce energy bills as well as carbon emissions, which is a particularly important consideration during the cost-of-living crisis.

Hydrogen heating and the introduction of green methane to the natural gas grid are potential interventions that were not included in this analysis. With respect to hydrogen heating, recent academic reviews find that compared with alternatives such as heat pumps, and district heating, hydrogen use for domestic heating has a worse economic profile, is more resource intensive, and is associated with larger environmental impacts⁵. With respect to green methane, costs were not found to be competitive with alternative technologies.

Considerations around decarbonisation of gas infrastructure are useful, but evidence suggests that their impact cannot be fully relied upon for reaching net-zero.⁶

Case studies from the Leeds PIPES network and Cosy Homes Oxfordshire offer insight into the ways the measures presented below can be turned into action by councils in the Belfast region.

Figure 10 – Belfast region’s domestic buildings emissions baseline with cost-effective, cost-neutral and technical potential scenarios

⁵ Rosenow, J., 2022. Is heating homes with hydrogen all but a pipe dream? An evidence review. *Joule*.

Riemer, M., Zheng, L., Eckstein, J., Wietschel, M., Pieton, N., & Kunze, R. (2022). Future hydrogen demand: A cross-sectoral, global meta-analysis. *Notes*.

⁶ CCC, 2018. Hydrogen in a low-carbon economy.

Table 9 - Domestic building's five year emissions reductions, annual energy savings and cumulative investments

		2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Emissions Reductions (ktCO ₂ e)	CE	30	114	212	246	287	328
	CN	48	184	348	411	479	547
	TP	129	499	977	1,200	1,400	1,600
Annual Energy Expenditure Savings (£, millions)	CE	78	146	159	155	150	146
	CN	115	216	238	234	230	227
	TP	218	421	482	493	505	516
Cumulative Investment (£, millions)	CE	152	685	761	761	761	761
	CN	894	4,021	4,468	4,468	4,469	4,469
	TP	3,305	14,143	15,783	15,883	15,980	16,076

Table 10 - Belfast region's most carbon-effective mitigation options for domestic buildings

Low Carbon Measure:	Absolute Emissions Reduction (ktCO ₂ e):	Cost per tonne (£)
Oil boilers to heat pumps in domestic buildings	9378	144
Whole house retrofits in domestic buildings	5778	488
Solar PV in domestic buildings	2011	345
Loft insulation in domestic buildings	1712	-431
External wall insulation in domestic buildings	1227	159
Heat pumps in domestic buildings	1128	753
Reduce household heating by 1° C in domestic buildings	781	-319
Cavity wall insulation in domestic buildings	769	-300
Gas combi-boilers in domestic buildings	725	277
Internal wall insulation in domestic buildings	692	-7

Table 11 - Belfast region's most cost-effective mitigation options for domestic buildings

Low Carbon Measure:	Cost per tonne (£)
A rated ovens in domestic buildings	-2975
Reduce heating for washing machines in domestic buildings	-1985
Turn unnecessary lighting off in domestic buildings	-1985
Integrated digital TVs in domestic buildings	-1820
A+ rated wet appliances in domestic buildings	-1758
Induction hobs in domestic buildings	-1620
Low energy lighting in domestic buildings	-1250
District heating networks in domestic buildings	-811
Tank insulation in domestic buildings	-548

Domestic Case Study 1 - Leeds PIPES Heat Network (*Led by local authority*)

The Leeds PIPES district heating network has successfully delivered a network of super-insulated underground pipes. The network is bringing lower costs and carbon heating and hot water to 1,800 residential properties, eight public buildings, and two commercial building, reusing heat generated at the nearby Recycling and Energy Recovery Facility (RERF).

Leeds City Council led the project with support from private sector partner Vital Energi. Construction was commenced on the assumption that new customers would connect once the infrastructure was completed, and by connections to social housing and the public sector. The council's ambition to become the UK's first net zero major city is supported by this project which recognises and delivers on the potential of heat networks.

The project received £4m of funding through the Leeds City Region Growth Deal, £5.8 from European Regional Development Funding (ERDF). The network now stretches around 26 kilometres, and mitigates 22,000 tonnes of CO₂ annually and has helped to create local jobs.

Impact

- Total investment in first phase of £9.8m
- Low carbon, low cost heat supplied to 1,800 homes
- 22,000 tonnes CO₂ saved annually

Domestic Case Study 2 - Cosy Homes Oxfordshire (*Enabled by local authority*)

Cosy Homes Oxfordshire is a private sector one-stop-shop home retrofit service, set up to make it simple for homeowners in Oxfordshire to improve the energy efficiency of their homes. The scheme was launched as a pilot in 2019 with support from BEIS as one of six supply chain demonstrators, bringing together customers and contractors to simplify the customer journey.

The scheme was developed using the RetrofitWorks co-operative model, and has been supported by organisations such as the Low Carbon Hub and Oxford City Council, who help with raising awareness among homeowners and building connections into communities.

As a one-stop-shop seeking to provide an end to end service for homeowners, Cosy Homes Oxfordshire takes a whole house approach to retrofit, having delivered 233 home assessments and 220 whole house plans since its launch. Interest from homeowners has been high but the scheme has run into issues with delivery due to supply chain limitations.

Impact

- 548 homes registered
- 220 whole house plans completed
- 23 retrofits in progress

(b). Public & Commercial Buildings

Low-carbon interventions for public and commercial buildings focus on similar measures to the domestic buildings sector – retrofit, fabric improvements and low-carbon heating. This sector encompasses the majority of non-domestic buildings in the region – office space, retail, hospitality, healthcare, hotels, non-retail, education and healthcare buildings.

Interventions in this sector in the Belfast region are significantly more cost-effective than in domestic buildings, partly due to commercial floorspace being more recently constructed than the majority of the housing stock. Interventions in this sector are modelled on a per metre-square basis, and aggregated across the Belfast region. Public and commercial floorspace is more heavily-weighted to certain local authorities, in particular in the city of Belfast, where the majority of interventions in this sector will be required.

Case studies from South Tyneside and Brighton demonstrate that councils can play a leading role turning the actions presented below into lower energy bills, new jobs and reduced GHG emissions.

Figure 11 - Belfast region's public and commercial buildings baseline with cost-effective, cost-neutral and technical potential scenarios

Table 12 - Belfast region's most carbon-effective mitigation options for public and commercial buildings

Low Carbon Measure:	Absolute Emissions Reduction (ktCO ₂ e):	Cost per tonne (£)
Fabric improvements in industrial buildings/warehouses	2018	81
Air tightness in retail buildings	764	120
Oil boilers to heat pumps in retail buildings	415	-441
Area-based commercial retrofits in retail buildings	355	-55
Oil boilers to heat pumps in office buildings	294	-945
Area-based commercial retrofits in industrial buildings/warehouses	260	-61
Replace single with double glazing in office buildings	191	-456
Heat recovery in retail buildings	144	279
Area-based commercial PV installations in industrial buildings/warehouses	109	-1497
Area-based commercial retrofits in office buildings	108	-550

Table 13 - Belfast region's most cost-effective mitigation options for public and commercial buildings

Low Carbon Measure:	Cost per tonne (£)
Electrical circuitry efficiency upgrades in retail buildings	-1430
AC upgrades in community centres	-1407
AC upgrades in healthcare buildings	-1404
AC upgrades in education buildings	-1394
AC upgrades in hotels	-1393
AC upgrades in non-retail buildings	-1383
AC upgrades in office buildings	-1377
Electrical circuitry efficiency upgrades in office buildings	-1371
Highly-efficient air cooling system in retail buildings	-1336
AC upgrades in retail buildings	-1302

Table 14 – Public and commercial buildings five year emissions reductions, annual energy savings and cumulative investments

		2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Emissions Reductions (ktCO ₂ e)	CE	22	85	161	189	221	252
	CN	25	95	176	203	236	270
	TP	34	128	238	274	320	366
Energy Savings (£, millions)	CE	38	78	81	84	86	89
	CN	50	99	102	105	109	112
	TP	65	127	131	135	139	143
Cumulative Investment (£, millions)	CE	194	436	678	920	969	969
	CN	302	679	1,057	1,434	1,510	1,510
	TP	935	2,103	3,272	4,440	4,674	4,674

Public and Commercial Buildings Case Study 1 –

Viking Energy Network Jarrow (VENJ)

The Viking Energy Network Jarrow (VENJ) is the first of three major district heating networks implemented by South Tyneside Council. The energy centre for VENJ will be sited on the bank of the River Tyne, and use water source heat pump (WSHP) technology fed by river water. The project will initially provide low cost, low carbon energy to nine connected commercial buildings.

Led by South Tyneside Council, VENJ will make a significant contribution to the city's pledged actions resulting from its climate emergency declaration and net zero 2030 target. The project is funded with a £3.5m grant provided by the European Regional Development Fund (ERDF), with additional management support provided by central government.

Once up and running, it is predicted that VENJ will save around £0.5m in fuel costs, and mitigate 1,035 tonnes of CO₂ annually. As an ERDF-funded project, it will also strive to stimulate local economic development through innovation and job creation.

Impact

- £3.5m grant funding from ERDF for its implementation
- £0.5m saved in fuel costs per year
- 1,035 tonnes of CO₂ mitigated per year

Public and Commercial Buildings Case Study 2 –

One Brighton

One Brighton is a sustainable housing development and community, built in line with Bioregional's One Planet Living sustainability framework which envisions a world where we live within the limits of the Earth's resources. The complex of 172 apartments is saving its residents money, while significantly reducing their resource consumption and carbon emissions.

The scheme was developed by Bioregional, building on learnings from BedZed, their first residential development. Bioregional has received endorsement from Brighton & Hove City Council and the Greater South East Net Zero Hub, but was delivered by private sector partners including architects Feilden Clegg Bradley Studios and contractors Denne.

One Bioregional achieved a 67% reduction in operational CO₂ emissions when compared to the UK's existing housing stock, with predictions that this would reach 89% by 2020. The scheme is also the UK's largest private car-free development, and implements nature into its design.

Impact

- 67% reduction in operational CO₂ compared to UK's existing housing stock
- Expected for this reduction to increase to 89% by 2020
- 31% of apartments are social or shared equity housing

(c). Transport

The transport system in the Belfast region is more reliant on car use on a per-trip basis than other urban areas in the UK, according to annual travel surveys. Recent upgrades to buses, park-and-ride schemes and the coming expansion of the Glider system should be lauded, and built upon to facilitate further mitigation in the transport sector.

Belfast city is consistently among the top 10 most congested cities in the UK. The prioritisation of active travel and public transport would not only ameliorate congestion, but would greatly contribute to the region in terms of co-benefits to air quality, health and quality of life. Pedestrianisation of streets in Belfast city centre provides a boost for local businesses and hospitality, as well as promoting active travel in the city centre that can be built upon.

Examples from Nottingham and Oxford provide examples the Belfast Region can draw upon to accelerate transport decarbonisation.

Figure 12 - Belfast region's transport emissions baseline with cost-effective, cost-neutral and technical potential scenarios⁷

⁷ In the transport sector the scale of potential savings is so large that all scenarios produce net economic returns. Consequently there is no cost-neutral scenario.

Table 15 - Belfast region's most carbon-effective mitigation options for the transport sector

Low Carbon Measure:	Absolute Emissions Reduction (ktCO ₂ e):	Cost per tonne (£)
Diesel light ordinary goods vehicle to electric ordinary goods vehicle	2350	8
Diesel heavy ordinary goods vehicle to electric ordinary goods vehicle	2140	2
Diesel light goods vehicles to electric light goods vehicles	1467	124
Small petrol car journeys to EV journeys	344	214
Small diesel car journeys to EV journeys	337	215
Large petrol car journeys to EV journeys	321	232
Medium petrol car journeys to EV journeys	315	242
Large diesel car journeys to EV journeys	314	233
Small diesel car journeys to walking journeys	311	592
Medium diesel car journeys to EV journeys	309	244

Table 16 - Belfast region's most cost-effective mitigation options for the transport sector

Low Carbon Measure:	Cost per tonne (£)
Large diesel car journeys to electric train journeys	-1862
Large petrol car journeys to electric bus journeys	-1830
Medium petrol car journeys to electric bus journeys	-1677
Small petrol car journeys to electric bus journeys	-1527
Large petrol car journeys to diesel bus journeys	-1190
Medium petrol car journeys to diesel bus journeys	-1062
Small petrol car journeys to diesel bus journeys	-669
Medium diesel car journeys to bicycle journeys	-617
Medium diesel car journeys to walking journeys	-607

Table 17 – Transport sector's five year emissions reductions, annual energy savings and cumulative investments

		2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Emissions Reductions (ktCO ₂ e)	CE	87	286	447	433	278	250
	TP	94	286	447	524	415	383
Annual Energy Expenditure Savings (£M)	CE	13	18	9	1	3	7
	TP	13	20	12	5	1	0.6
Cumulative Investment (£M)	CE	123	176	182	216	216	218
	TP	161	244	255	309	309	315

Transport Case Study 1 - Nottingham Workplace Parking Levy (*Led by local authority*)

Nottingham City Council led this trailblazing example of a Workplace Parking Levy (WPL) which charges employers that provide workplace parking. The levy tackles congestion two-fold by incentivising employers to reduce provision for parking and promote other modes of commuting, while also helping to fund infrastructure projects such as improved public transport.

This initiative received significant funding support from central government, but was pioneered by Nottingham City Council, who set up a dedicated consultancy to handle the development and implementation of the levy. Because it was the first of its kind in the western hemisphere, the development of the levy faced high upfront costs and took twelve years to implement, but levies elsewhere would benefit from the new ground broken by this initiative.

The WPL generates £9m revenue annually for the city, and its running costs are less than 5% of this figure. A total of £83m in revenue has been generated since its launch in 2011, much of which has funded public transport upgrades including part-funding a 17.5km tram extension.

Impact

- £1.8m invested in its development and implementation
- £83m revenue generated by the levy
- 7840 tonnes CO2 saved from public transport investment
- 40% of commutes now made by public transport

Transport Case Study 2 - Energy Superhub Oxford (*Enabled by local authority*)

As one of three demonstrator projects part-funded by central government to showcase an integrated and innovative approach to developing smart local energy systems, Energy Superhub Oxford (ESO) will be a blueprint for other cities to follow in the net zero transition. The project combines technologies and business models to decarbonise power, transport and heat.

ESO is a private-public consortium of six partners led by Pivot Power, along with business, public, and academic organisations. Oxford City Council is a key partner and supports the project as a critical means of delivering the city's net zero target for 2040.

Oxford City Council has received £1.6m for its role in the project as part of the £10m funding provided by the government's Prospering from the Energy Revolution (PFER) programme. In total, ESO is a £41m project, aiming to mitigate 10,000 tonnes of CO2 emissions annually, which is roughly equivalent to taking 2,000 cars off the road.

Impact

- £41m total invested in the project
- £10m funding from the government's PFER challenge
- 50MW hybrid battery, 8km EV charging network, 100 ground source heat pumps
- Aims to eliminate 10,000 tonnes of CO2 annually

(d). Industry

The industrial sector in the Belfast region contributes significantly to its overall annual emissions. Its emissions have fallen by almost 50% on 2000 levels, but ambitious interventions are required to decarbonise the sector. Vehicle manufacturing and food and drink production are key sources of industrial emissions from the region.

Case studies from Trafford and Devon demonstrate that local governments can play a leading role supporting decarbonisation of the industry sector.

Figure 13 - Belfast region's industry emissions baseline with cost-effective, cost-neutral and technical potential scenarios

Table 18 - Belfast region's most carbon-effective mitigation options for the industry sector

Low Carbon Measure:	Absolute Emissions Reduction (ktCO2e):	Cost per tonne (£)
Condensing and insulation measures to boilers and steam piping in industry	2869	339
Improving efficiency of boilers and steam piping in industry	1962	353
Pump upgrades, repairs and maintenance in industry	848	155
Fan correction, repairs, and upgrades in industry	605	149
Compressed air systems in industry	568	141
Compressors and variable speed systems in industry	437	138
Furnace efficiency and heat recovery mechanisms in industry	359	363
Refrigeration efficiency and technical upgrades in industry	181	350

Table 19 - Belfast region's most cost-effective mitigation options for the industry sector

Low Carbon Measure:	MAC Value (£/tCO ₂ e)
Furnace efficiency and heat recovery mechanisms in industry	-363
Improving efficiency of boilers and steam piping in industry	-353
Refrigeration efficiency and technical upgrades in industry	-350
Condensing and insulation measures to boilers and steam piping in industry	-339
Pump upgrades, repairs and maintenance in industry	-155
Fan correction, repairs, & upgrades in industry	-149
Compressed air systems in industry	-141
Compressors and variable speed systems in industry	-138

Table 20 – Industry sector's five year emissions reductions, annual energy savings and cumulative investments

		2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Emissions Reductions (ktCO ₂ e)	CE	69	212	239	221	200	198
	CN	114	363	411	419	392	388
	TP	195	634	722	769	728	721
Energy Savings (£, millions)	CE	14	76	131	150	168	189
	CN	19	98	172	203	232	262
	TP	35	206	382	474	555	633
Cumulative Investment (£, millions)	CE	216	897	1,504	1,504	1,504	1,504
	CN	349	1,881	2,853	2,853	2,853	2,853
	TP	904	5,582	9,306	9,306	9,306	9,306

Industry Case Study 1 - Trafford Green Hydrogen

Trafford Green Hydrogen is a green hydrogen fuel production facility which will produce fuel for heating, industry and transport using renewable energy. The facility is part of the Trafford Low Carbon Energy Park which is sited on an old industrial power station. This site includes Europe's largest liquid air energy storage scheme and one of the UK's largest battery storage schemes.

A range of partners including Trafford Metropolitan Borough Council and Greater Manchester Combined Authority signed and delivered on a memorandum of understanding, helping the private sector lead Carlton Power to advance the project. In 2022, support was also given by the council through the granting of planning permission for the facility's development.

Once fully up and running, the facility will have a capacity of 200MW, enough to take 8,000 petrol cars off the road per year. Its initial 20MW capacity will mitigate 20,000 tonnes CO₂ in the Manchester region and beyond, and support the UK's net zero energy transition. Trafford Green Hydrogen will also help to create and sustain local green job opportunities.

Impact

- 20,000 tonnes CO₂ mitigated annually from initial phase
- 8,000 petrol cars taken off the road annually from ultimate 200MW capacity

Industry Case Study 2 - Devon Commercial Recycling of EV Batteries

Devon is leading the way in the commercial recycling of EV batteries, with Devon County Council supporting a scale-up of the private sector company Altitech's processes to a commercial scale. The method recovers over 95% of spent batteries' critical metals at a quality which means they can be reused in the production of new batteries, supporting the transition to net zero through sustainable electrification technology and circular processes.

Devon County Council's Green Innovation Fund has provided capital funding for equipment needed for a commercial-scale process, and revenue funding for employing and training new staff. Funding of £169,384 allowed this piloting of the UK's first battery recycling facility.

Altitech expects to have created 250 new green jobs by 2026, allowing the facility to recycle battery waste from more than 150,000 EVs. In its first year of operation, the facility is forecast to recycle 250 batteries, mitigating 2,737 tonnes of CO₂. As a circular model, it will also help to retain value in the local economy while reducing mining emissions and toxic waste creation.

Impact

- £169,384 of funding from Devon County Council
- 150,000 EV batteries recycled by 2026
- 2,737 tonnes of CO₂ mitigated in its first year of operation

(e): Land Use

The land-use sector – comprising Land-use, Land-use Change and Forestry (LULUCF) and agriculture – accounts for emissions and removals primarily from wetlands, forestry, grassland, cropland, urban encroachment and animal agriculture. This sector is unique as it has the potential to be an overall carbon sink (ie sequester more CO₂e than it emits), but it currently contributes 32% of the region’s overall emissions. It is notable that the land-use sector’s emissions are not currently projected to fall meaningfully over time under current policies.

Land-use area breakdowns highlight the scale of agricultural land used for animal grazing across the Belfast region. Interventions in this sector focus on improvements on a per-farm basis to reduce emissions from crop soils and animals, for example improved animal feed and optimising soil PH. A complementary set of interventions shift agricultural land to forestry and the restoration of peatlands.

The land-use sector presents a high degree of variability, and interventions must consider the range of emissions sources and intervention opportunities. Joined-up, full system approaches to mitigation in farming and land-management require substantial planning and monitoring, but are necessary to reduce emissions from this sector.

The engagement and buy-in from communities is particularly crucial in this context given the effect interventions could have on farmers’ lives and livelihoods. Changes to more ecologically-friendly farming techniques must be supported by local communities at each stage of the process in order for low-carbon measures to be implemented in an effective, equitable manner. Support schemes are currently underway in England (such as the Environmental Land Management Scheme) and the ‘Forests for our Future’ initiative in Northern Ireland a Department of Agriculture, Environment & Rural Affairs (DAERA) programme, to incentivise farmers to adopt sustainable practices and to introduce reforestation and afforestation.

The challenges associated with achieving carbon reductions in this sector are unique and complex. In the buildings sector, there are clear benefits to homeowners (reduced energy bills), communities (reduced fuel poverty), the wider economy (employment), and society (improved air quality). In the land-use sector, by contrast, changes in land-use could lead to negative consequences for the rural economy and ways of living in the absence of significant government support and meaningful structural economic change.

Important to note, that the accounting approach taken by this analysis, and followed by UK Government, the CCC and the *Global Protocol for Community-Scale Greenhouse Gas Emission Inventories*, ascribe direct and indirect emissions from land-use and agriculture to the local area. A consumption-based approach, by contrast, would account for these emissions where agricultural products are consumed by households. A consumption-based approach would therefore potentially significantly reduce the GHG footprint of the Belfast region.

The challenges for implementing change in this sector are varied, and will require substantial consideration, public support and political momentum to enact. The protests in several European countries in 2022, around mandated nitrogen emissions reductions for farmers highlight the risk of pushing policy at short-notice without proper consultation.

Some of the main challenges around effecting change in this sector can be summarised within the following categories:

- i) **Technical** – The practical challenges include identifying, selecting and implementing appropriate low and zero carbon measures. Accurate, consistent measurements and considerable resources are necessary to design, deliver and maintain these carbon reductions.
- ii) **Cultural and behavioural** – Lifestyles, diets, livelihoods and culture in Northern Ireland are tied to rural ways of living and existing land-use practices. Significant, widespread interventions are undoubtedly going to affect the lives, behaviours and attitudes of a significant portion of Northern Ireland’s population.
- iii) **Policy and governance** – Policies surrounding agriculture, forestry, and the rural sector in general are the responsibility of DAERA in Northern Ireland and not the local authority. This isn’t to say that the local authority and its communities can’t be effective in enacting change. However, it does create an additional institutional hurdle which must be overcome through wide-ranging collaboration and planning. In this way, another specific issue around agricultural interventions is the conacre system. Estimates suggest around 30% of farmland each year is rented in short-term tenancy agreements, which has been a barrier to land-ownership and hinders effective uptake of long-term strategies such as improving soil health and biodiversity levels.

This report’s analysis is a technical assessment of the costs and carbon mitigation benefits of possible interventions. Modelling thus serves to inform discussion and policy engagement while acknowledging that a wider social, cultural and political context of land-use discussions is not directly considered by analysis.

Figure 15 shows the low, medium and high ambition scenarios adopted for the land-use sector. The sub-sectors have been modelled individually, with figure 15 demonstrating overall mitigation across sub-sectors. The bulk of mitigation comes from changes to animal agriculture, including low-carbon measures such as improved animal nutrition, soil health improvements, and afforestation of grazing land. The scenarios are:

- **Low Ambition** – Reduction in urban encroachment, restoration of wetlands degraded from peat extraction, significant implementations of emissions reductions from ruminant livestock through improved nutrition, supplements and improved farming practices.
- **Medium Ambition** – Includes above measures as well as a shift of **21.5%** from animal agriculture to afforested land to reach overall net-zero emissions within the land-use sector.
- **High Ambition** – Includes interventions from low ambition scenario, and modelled shifts from the CCC’s most ambitious land-use pathway – namely a **50%** shift from agricultural land to afforested land. Recent analysis from the CCC’s high ambition scenario suggests a 50% reduction in livestock numbers specifically for Northern Ireland.⁸

⁸ <https://www.theccc.org.uk/publication/advice-report-the-path-to-a-net-zero-northern-ireland/>

Figure 14 - Belfast region's simplified land-use area breakdown estimate by sub-sector

Figure 15 - Belfast region's land-use emissions baseline with low, medium and high ambition scenarios

Table 21 - Belfast region's most carbon-effective mitigation options for the land-use sector

Low Carbon Measure:	Absolute Emissions Reduction (ktCO ₂ e):	Cost per tonne (£)
Afforestation of grazing land	45480	14
Wetlands - High ambition restoration	3556	24
Reduce urban encroachment on natural areas	3532	-
Wetlands - Medium ambition restoration	2651	19
Miscanthus planting	2215	13
Methane inhibitors in animal feed for dairy cows	1761	36
Wetlands - Low ambition restoration	1094	32
Nitrate supplements in animal feed for sheep	1087	278
Methane inhibitors in animal feed for beef cows	904	54
Silvopastoral agroforestry	817	87

Table 22 - Belfast region's most cost-effective mitigation options for the land-use sector

Low Carbon Measure:	Cost per tonne (£)
Optimal pH lining	-2
Manure spreading on farmland	-1
Low tilling practices	0
Miscanthus planting	13
Afforestation of grazing land	14
Cover crops	17
Wetlands - Medium ambition restoration	19
Wetlands - High ambition restoration	24
Wetlands - Low ambition restoration	32
Methane inhibitors in animal feed for dairy cows	36

Table 23 - Land-use sector's five year emissions reductions and cumulative investments

		2025	2030	2035	2040	2045	2050
Emissions	Low	93	280	320	695	751	757
Reductions (kt CO ₂ e)	Medium	187	499	566	1,222	1,336	1,348
	High	284	730	827	1,809	1,972	1,989
Cumulative Investment (£ millions)	Low	104	242	327	401	475	490
	Medium	167	394	527	640	754	777
	High	250	579	764	920	1,076	1,108

Land-Use Case Study 1 - Garron Peatland Restoration

The Garron Plateau in County Antrim contains the largest area of intact blanket bog in Northern Ireland. Significant restoration efforts have been carried out by the Royal Society for the Protection of Birds (RSPB) and NI Water on roughly 500 ha of peat from 2010. These peatlands were in a damaged condition due to general degradation and grazing. The area is particularly important as it provides drinking water for an estimated 14,000 homes in Ballymena and the surrounding area, and is a designated Special Area of Conservation (SAC).

The RSPB, NI Water, and the NI Environment Agency have been supported by the Northern Irish Department of Agriculture, Environment and Rural Affairs (DAERA), the Republic of Ireland's Department of Housing, Planning and Local Government, and the Special EU Programme's Body. Restoration efforts have been successful, with large areas of peat now classified as rewetted or restored, due to interventions such as deforestation, damming and rewetting.

Impact

- 10,034 t CO₂e mitigated annually from 2016
- Projected 17,918 t CO₂e mitigated annually from 2045
- Reduction in water treatment costs due to improvements in water quality
- Increased employment opportunities

Land-Use Case Study 2 - ArcZero Farming

Accelerating Ruminant Carbon Zero (ARCZero) is a farmer-led, European Innovation Partnership Project in Northern Ireland which aims to promote the measuring and management of carbon flows, to empower farmers to reduce emissions at the farm level. It aims to accurately estimate total carbon flux through the complete assessment of the farm's carbon stocks and sequestration potential. Accurate baseline emissions can be calculated through creating individual, whole-farm carbon balance sheets through the measurement of carbon stocks in soils, hedges and trees.

From accurate baseline emissions estimates, future management practices can be examined and prioritised to increase sequestration and sustainable land-management.

Through partnerships with DAERA, the European Agricultural Fund for Rural Development, the Rural Development Programme, Queen's University Belfast and private-sector organisations such as Devenish Nutrition, 7 farms are currently analysing their whole-farm carbon footprint and enacting a series of low-carbon measures on an individualised basis.

Impact

- Increased education, engagement and community buy-in from farmers across NI
- Introduction of low-carbon measures such as switching to multi-species sward grazing
- Accurate net emissions mapping at the farm-level of carbon inputs and outputs
- Individualised planning to prioritise and monitor carbon mitigation

BELFAST REGION'S NET-ZERO EMISSIONS PATHWAY

If the Belfast region were to implement all possible measures across the buildings, industrial and transport sectors, there would be a remaining shortfall of **1.4 Mt CO₂e** in 2050. There are a number of options to address these remaining emissions. New technologies, including green hydrogen boilers for heating, new processes in industry and long-range battery and hydrogen transport vehicles may be available in the coming decade. These technologies, however, are currently unproven and significant issues surrounding their mass introduction are likely to arise. An alternative approach would leverage the opportunity in the region's rural areas to unlock huge mitigation and sequestration potential.

To cover the 1.4 Mt of CO₂e in 2050 the Belfast region could afforest **42%** of the land currently used for animal agriculture. This equates to **25%** of all land across the Belfast region and is less than the 50% reduction implied by CCC modelling. The tree-planting modelled consists of mixed woodland, a woodland type that recreates the kind of forest that would have covered large parts of Northern Ireland until the mid-19th century.

This ambitious target presents numerous challenges, namely providing support and uptake to rural communities as well as land-management challenges. The benefits of this approach, however, are also large. In addition to helping the region meet its carbon targets, the co-benefits for the environment and population in the region include improvements to air quality, water quality, biodiversity levels, soil health, reductions in flooding-risks and improvements in mental health.

Carbon emissions could be cut further still through the adoption of behavioural and consumption-based changes such as the promotion of active travel (e.g. walking and cycling), reductions in meat and dairy consumption and the generation of food waste, and reduced consumption of concrete and steel, with more emphasis on green infrastructure. Such consumption-based changes – which would impact on the broader Scope 3 carbon footprint of the region – is an important area for future work.

Figure 16 - Belfast region's remaining sectoral emissions and net-emissions pathway to net-zero by 2050

NEXT STEPS FOR THE BELFAST REGION

i) Accept the Need for High Levels of Ambition

The Belfast region has to take ambitious actions to reduce its carbon emissions if it is to stay within its share of the global carbon budget consistent with avoiding dangerous climate change. Although the region's emissions have fallen by **30%** since 1990, it needs to accelerate and intensify its decarbonisation efforts if it is to meet its science-based targets. The good news is that the analysis shows that it is possible for the Belfast region to reach the goal of reaching net zero by 2050.

Across the different sectors, focusing on the Level 1 (cost-effective) and Level 2 (cost-neutral) options will require substantial investment, but the potential is there to cut the region's projected emissions in 2050 by **22%** at no net cost to the region. Adopting these options will also create roughly **26,421** employment years and a range of wide social, economic and environmental co-benefits across the region. However, the Belfast region needs to go further to explore the Level 3 (technically viable) options that do not pay for themselves directly, even if they do generate significant co-benefits in the form of reduced fuel poverty, reduced congestion, improved air quality and enhanced comfort.

It is also important to place the plans for the Belfast region in the context of the rest of Northern Ireland and developing an agreed model of action planning with other City and Growth Deals and local and central government partners.. The recent Climate Change Act should be celebrated as an important step forward for Northern Ireland's climate-action journey, while recognising that more ambitious, specific and locally-led action is also necessary.

The Belfast region comprises **60%** of Northern Ireland's population, is responsible for **42%** of all territorial emissions, and **33%** of the land area and there is therefore a responsibility to advocate for and lead the way in enacting climate action in NI. In order to match emissions reductions and legislative progress in other areas of the UK, as well as the Republic of Ireland, urgent and ambitious action is required across all sectors.

ii) Focus on the Main Priorities

Although change will be required across the region, it will also be important to focus on and to identify priorities for action. **68%** of the Belfast region's carbon footprint comes from domestic buildings, the land-use sector and industry. It therefore makes sense for the Belfast region to focus the bulk of its decarbonisation efforts on these areas. Key initiatives in the buildings sector should be based on ambitious and accelerated retrofit schemes for existing homes and buildings, and the highest energy efficiency standards for new homes and buildings. Key initiatives in the transport sector should include clear plans for demand management and active travel such as walking and cycling, and energetic policies to promote the wider use of public transport. The switch from internal combustion engines to electric vehicles should also be encouraged.

iii) Take a Joined-Up Approach to Change

Although it is important to prioritise, the change necessary to deliver the Belfast region's climate and wider priorities requires a joined-up or 'whole-system' approach. This recognises the connections that exist between different sectors like housing, transport, and energy, the overlapping barriers to change within and between these sectors, and the opportunity and need to involve all stakeholders in delivering maximum positive outcomes for all. It requires a shift in mindset away from delivering individual projects in isolation, toward understanding the connections between them as a way of driving momentum and increasing value for money. This involves longer-term planning, in parallel with (not at the expense of) getting on with quick wins. Managing this type of change across the six local authorities and the region in general will involve deliberate shifts in culture and working arrangements to support capacity building and deeper collaboration.

iv) Understand Roles and Share Responsibilities

Change is required across the entire area if the region is to realise its ambitions on climate change. Of course, local authorities have to be a central part of the process – through their efforts to decarbonise their estates and vehicle stocks, through their use of power in policy and planning, and through their ability to convene conversations and catalyse change. Research⁹ suggests that in the UK, local authorities can directly affect 2-5% of emissions in their locality, but have clear influence over an additional 30% of emissions, and play an important role encouraging action over a further 30% of emissions (these figures are likely to be significantly lower in NI given the more restricted remit of Councils). Determining where the local authorities have leverage to directly and indirectly affect emissions can help to shape the way they approach taking action and maximise the use of their resources. To extend its influence, the region should build partnerships with other public sector bodies and with businesses, third sector organisations and communities across the region. Only by building a sense of shared responsibility and collective action can the necessary far-reaching and cross-cutting changes be delivered.

v) Develop a Positive Vision

It will be very hard to deliver the changes required if they are somehow at odds with the region's broader priorities or with people's own aspirations. As the wider case for climate action is developed it will be important to use that case to develop a positive overarching vision of how cutting carbon can support a thriving region. Ambitious climate actions can also enhance comfort, cut fuel bills, generate jobs, tackle fuel poverty, enhance business productivity and resilience, address congestion and improve air quality. With a positive vision climate change can be mainstreamed into key areas of regional development relating to economic development, housing, transport, health, planning and so on.

⁹ <https://www.theccc.org.uk/publication/local-authorities-and-the-sixth-carbon-budget/>

vi) Build Legitimacy

Cross-cutting climate actions will depend on political, public and business support. Change will be much easier with stable, cross-party political support. More broadly, it is vitally important that the people and businesses of the Belfast region feel that they have been involved in the process and will benefit from the outcomes of decisions relating to climate change. Establishing an open, inclusive, cross-community and cross-sectoral climate commission could help to secure active buy-in. Running a Citizens Jury to actively engage with diverse communities and perspectives from across the region can help to ensure that all voices are heard and that a sense of legitimacy is built and maintained.

vii) Assess Readiness and Build a Pipeline

This report has set out an evidence base on the technical and economic viability of a wide range of decarbonisation options for the Belfast region. Clearly though the mere presence of the opportunities does not mean that they will actually be taken. The Belfast region should assess how ready it is to adopt the different options – considering not only technical but also policy, social, financial and institutional readiness. Where the region is fully ready, action can be initiated immediately – but any blockers preventing progress should be identified so that targeted actions can be introduced to build readiness over time. Where the blockers can be easily addressed then near-term actions can be planned, but where there are more structural barriers to change longer-term processes of capacity building or lobbying of national government may be required. In this way, a pipeline of actions can be developed that can form the basis of a short, medium and longer term action plan.

viii) Explore Business Models and Build Capabilities for Programme Development

Some text

As the investment needs associated with especially the more challenging levels of action are significant, it will be important to understand financing options and business models, and to build capacities for innovative approaches that can stimulate investment. Integrating climate change into key policy and planning decisions that incentivise investments that help the region to decarbonise – or that disincentivise decisions that do the opposite – can also reduce the need for climate finance. Mainstreaming climate considerations into existing flows of investment in the region – especially relating to housing, regeneration and transport – will substantially lower the need for explicit climate investment. This is as important for businesses and households across the region as it is for the local authorities themselves.

The relationships between different actors – those financing action, those being paid to take actions or develop projects, and those who are managing projects and procuring work – will be different for different climate actions. In the transport sector, for example, the way projects are developed and financed for public transport, bike lanes and electric vehicle charging will each be unique. Mapping different business model options and carefully considering their merits will be important to determining the best approaches.

Building capacities or platforms for programme and project development will also be crucial. Such a platform should identify innovations and emerging initiatives, consolidate and de-risk them and help to develop appropriate business and delivery models so that they can be

turned into investable initiatives. The Belfast region is not alone in doing this – there is much to be gained through collaboration and the transfer of best practice from other localities.

ix) Evaluate and Learn from Progress

Having capacity to evaluate and learn from the initiatives already underway within the Belfast region – and also more broadly – can help to ensure that best practice develops and spreads across the region. It is vital though that the Belfast region monitors and openly presents data charting its progress towards its carbon targets. As important as it is to be positive, actions are often driven by transparency and accountability, and early feedback can help the Belfast region to ensure that it stays on track as it moves towards net zero.

x) Celebrate and Build on Success

One of the most effective ways of building momentum is to raise awareness of the wide-range of climate-related initiatives that are already underway across the region. Some of these will be explicitly focused on climate and decarbonisation, but many others will have integrated a climate dimension into a broader project or initiative. Collating a suite of case studies and success stories can help to create a sense of positivity. Looking forward, drawing together a list of the range of commitments already made and of the projects and programmes that are planned can be crucial in establishing momentum.

APPENDICES

Appendix 1 – Glossary and acronyms

Carbon budget – Maximum cumulative amount of CO₂e able to be emitted while remaining within a certain temperature threshold.

Cold appliances – Refrigerators, freezers.

Cost-effective – Measures which save more money than they cost over their lifetime

Cost-neutral - Measures which are equal in costs and savings over their lifetime

Technical potential - Measures which cost more money than they save over their lifetime

Offsets – Balancing carbon emissions in one area/sector by sequestering carbon elsewhere

Passivhaus/Passive House – Very highly-efficient building standards to minimise energy demand

Scope 1 emissions – Direct emissions from sources within the local authority

Scope 2 emissions – Indirect emissions from heat and electricity used within the area of analysis, from production facilities outside the area of analysis

Scope 3 emissions – Indirect emissions emitted from outside the area of analysis, during the production and transport of goods and services

Wet appliances – Dishwashers, washing machines.

Whole house retrofit – Comprehensive, in-depth approach to improving energy efficiency in energy-intensive homes.

CO₂ – Carbon Dioxide

CO₂E - Carbon Dioxide Equivalent

EV – Electric Vehicle

ICE – Internal Combustion Vehicles

IPCC – Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

Kt – Kilotonne (1,000 tonnes)

LULUCF – Land-Use, Land-Use Change and Forestry

Mt – Megatonne (1,000,000 tonnes)

SBTs – Science-Based Targets

Appendix 2 – Local authority sectoral baseline emissions, projected emissions and SBTs

a) Antrim and Newtownabbey –

Antrim and Newtownabbey’s total carbon budget is **6.5** mt CO₂e. These emissions have decreased by **31%** since **1990**, and are forecast to decrease by a total of **47%** by 2050, on 1990 levels. Their current emissions are **1.6** mt CO₂e per annum, meaning that their budget will be used up within **6** years, by the end of **2028**. Antrim and Newtownabbey should aim to stick to the following SBTs (on 1990 levels):

- 2025 – 63%
- 2030 – 88%
- 2035 – 96%
- 2040 – 98.6%
- 2045 – 99.5%
- 2050 – 100%

Figure 17 - Antrim and Newtownabbey's historic and projected baseline emissions

Figure 18 - Antrim and Newtownabbey's science-based targets for emissions reductions

b) Ards and North Down –

Ards and North Down’s total carbon budget is **7.2** mt CO₂e. These emissions have decreased by **29%** since **1990**, and are forecast to decrease by a total of **43%** by 2050, on 1990 levels. Their current emissions are 998 kt CO₂e per annum, meaning that their budget will be used up within **8** years, by the end of **2030**. Ards and North Down should aim to stick to the following SBTs (reductions on 1990 levels):

- 2025 – 49%
- 2030 – 72%
- 2035 – 85%
- 2040 – 93%
- 2045 – 98%
- 2050 – 100%

Figure 19 - Ards and North Down's historic and projected baseline emissions

Figure 20 - Ards and North Down's science-based targets for emissions reductions

c) Belfast –

Belfast's total carbon budget is **12.8** mt CO₂e. These emissions have decreased by **54%** since **1990**, and are forecast to decrease by a total of **65%** by 2050, on 1990 levels. Their current emissions are 1.5 mt CO₂e per annum, meaning that their budget will be used up within **11** years, during **2033**. Belfast should aim to stick to the following SBTs (reductions on 1990 levels):

- 2025 – 64%
- 2030 – 78%
- 2035 – 87%
- 2040 – 92%
- 2045 – 95%
- 2050 – 100%

Figure 21 - Belfast's historic and projected baseline emissions

Figure 22 - Belfast's science-based targets for emissions reductions

d) Lisburn and Castlereagh –

Lisburn and Castlereagh’s total carbon budget is **7.2** mt CO₂e. These emissions have decreased by **19%** since **1990**, and are forecast to decrease by a total of **29%** by 2050, on 1990 levels. Their current emissions are 1.3 mt CO₂e per annum, meaning that their budget will be used up within **7** years, in **2029**. Lisburn and Castlereagh should aim to stick to the following SBTs (reductions on 1990 levels):

- 2025 – 48%
- 2030 – 77%
- 2035 – 90%
- 2040 – 96%
- 2045 – 99%
- 2050 – 100%

Figure 23 - Lisburn and Castlereagh's historic and projected baseline emissions

Figure 24 - Lisburn and Castlereagh's science-based targets for emissions reductions

e) Mid and East Antrim –

Mid and East Antrim’s total carbon budget is **6.2** mt CO₂e. These emissions have decreased by **24%** since **1990**, and are forecast to decrease by a total of **38%** by 2050, on 1990 levels. Their current emissions are 1.7 mt CO₂e per annum, meaning that their budget will be used up within **4** years, by the end of **2026**. Mid and East Antrim should aim to stick to the following SBTs (reductions on 1990 levels):

- 2025 – 63%
- 2030 – 89%
- 2035 – 97%
- 2040 – 99.1%
- 2045 – 99.8%
- 2050 – 100%

Figure 25 - Mid and East Antrim’s historic and projected baseline emissions

Figure 26 – Mid and East Antrim’s science-based targets for emissions reductions

f) Newry, Mourne and Down –

Newry, Mourne and Down’s total carbon budget is **8.5** mt CO₂e. These emissions have decreased by **19%** since **1990**, and are forecast to decrease by a total of 32% by 2050, on 1990 levels. Their current emissions are 1.9 mt CO₂e per annum, meaning that their budget will be used up within **5** years, during **2027**. Newry, Mourne and Down should aim to stick to the following SBTs (reductions on 1990 levels):

- 2025 – 54%
- 2030 – 83%
- 2035 – 94%
- 2040 – 98%
- 2045 – 99%
- 2050 – 100%

Figure 27- Newry, Mourne and Down's current and projected baseline emissions

Figure 28 - Newry, Mourne and Down's science-based targets for emissions reductions

Appendix 3 – Local authority land use breakdowns

Antrim and Newtownabbey

Animal Agri Other Forestry Cropland
Urban Grassland Peatlands

Lisburn and Castlereagh

Forestry Cropland Animal Agri Urban
Grassland Other Peatlands

Ards and North Down

Forestry Cropland Animal Agri Urban
Grassland Other Peatlands

Mid and East Antrim

Forestry Cropland Animal Agri Urban
Grassland Other Peatlands

Belfast

Forestry Cropland Animal Agri Urban
Grassland Other Peatlands

Newry, Mourne and Down

Forestry Cropland Animal Agri
Urban Grassland Other Peatlands

Appendix 4 – Land-use sub-sector mitigation pathways

Figure 29 - Low, medium and high ambition mitigation pathways for the forestry sub-sector

Figure 30- Low, medium and high ambition mitigation pathways for the animal agriculture sub-sector

Figure 29 - Low, medium and high ambition mitigation pathways for the cropland sub-sector

Figure 30 - Low, medium and high ambition mitigation pathways for the wetlands sub-sector

Figure 31 - Change in emissions by land-use sub-sector from baseline to high ambition scenario

Appendix 5– Belfast Region’s league table of most carbon-effective options

Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Carbon mitigated (kt CO ₂ e):	Cost per tonne (£):
Land-use	Afforestation of grazing land	45480	14
Domestic	Oil boilers to heat pumps in domestic buildings	9378	144
Domestic	Whole house retrofits in domestic buildings	5778	488
Land-use	Wetlands - High ambition restoration	3556	24
Land-use	Reduce urban encroachment on natural areas	3532	-
Industry	Condensing and insulation measures to boilers and steam piping in industry	2870	339
Land-use	Wetlands - Medium ambition restoration	2651	19
Transport	Diesel light ordinary goods vehicle to electric ordinary goods vehicle	2351	-8
Land-use	Miscanthus planting	2215	13
Transport	Diesel heavy ordinary goods vehicle to electric ordinary goods vehicle	2140	-2
Public and Commercial	Fabric improvements in industrial buildings/warehouses	2019	-81
Domestic	Solar PV in domestic buildings	2011	345
Industry	Improving efficiency of boilers and steam piping in industry	1962	353
Land-use	Methane inhibitors in animal feed for dairy cows	1761	36
Domestic	Loft insulation in domestic buildings	1713	-431
Transport	Diesel light goods vehicles to electric light goods vehicles	1467	-124
Domestic	External wall insulation in domestic buildings	1228	159
Domestic	Heat pumps in domestic buildings	1128	753
Land-use	Wetlands - Low ambition restoration	1094	32
Land-use	Nitrate supplements in animal feed for sheep	1087	278
Domestic	Cavity wall insulation in domestic buildings	952	-300
Land-use	Methane inhibitors in animal feed for beef cows	904	54
Industry	Pump upgrades, repairs and maintenance in industry	848	155
Land-use	Silvopastoral agroforestry	817	87
Land-use	Cover crops	792	17

Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Carbon mitigated (kt CO ₂ e):	Cost per tonne (£):
Domestic	Reduce household heating by 1 C in domestic buildings	781	-319
Public and Commercial	Air tightness in retail buildings	765	-120
Domestic	Gas combi-boilers in domestic buildings	726	277
Domestic	Internal wall insulation in domestic buildings	693	-7
Land-use	Manure spreading on farmland	684	-1
Industry	Fan correction, repairs, and upgrades in industry	605	149
Industry	Compressed air systems in industry	568	141
Industry	Compressors and variable speed systems in industry	437	138
Land-use	Optimal pH lining	436	-2
Public and Commercial	Oil boilers to heat pumps in retail buildings	416	441
Domestic	Floor insulation in domestic buildings	408	-220
Industry	Furnace efficiency and heat recovery mechanisms in industry	360	363
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial retrofits in retail buildings	355	-55
Transport	Small petrol car journeys to EV journeys	345	-214
Transport	Small diesel car journeys to EV journeys	337	-215
Land-use	Hedgerow expansion	331	157
Transport	Large petrol car journeys to EV journeys	321	-232
Transport	Medium petrol car journeys to EV journeys	316	-242
Transport	Large diesel car journeys to EV journeys	314	-233
Transport	Small diesel car journeys to walking journeys	311	-592
Transport	Medium diesel car journeys to EV journeys	309	-244
Public and Commercial	Oil boilers to heat pumps in office buildings	295	945
Transport	Large diesel car journeys to walking journeys	290	-557
Transport	Diesel bus journeys to electric bus journeys	286	-146
Transport	Medium diesel car journeys to walking journeys	285	-608
Transport	Small diesel car journeys to bicycle journeys	284	-588

Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Carbon mitigated (kt CO ₂ e):	Cost per tonne (£):
Transport	Large diesel car journeys to bicycle journeys	265	-578
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial retrofits in industrial buildings/warehouses	261	-61
Transport	Medium diesel car journeys to bicycle journeys	260	-617
Domestic	Top-up loft insulation in domestic buildings	221	-291
Domestic	Triple glazing in domestic buildings	217	2188
Land-use	Nitrate supplements in animal feed for pigs	204	232
Land-use	Silvoarable agroforestry	200	156
Land-use	Low tilling practices	195	0
Public and Commercial	Replace single with double glazing in office buildings	191	456
Industry	Refrigeration efficiency and technical upgrades in industry	182	350
Domestic	Passivehaus standards in new domestic buildings	174	3462
Public and Commercial	Heat recovery in retail buildings	144	-279
Domestic	Lowering thermostats in domestic buildings	136	-345
Domestic	Solar thermal in domestic buildings	110	1287
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial PV installations in industrial buildings/warehouses	110	1497
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial retrofits in office buildings	108	-550
Domestic	Low energy lighting in domestic buildings	104	-1250
Public and Commercial	Air tightness in office buildings	103	-126
Domestic	Tank insulation in domestic buildings	70	-548
Public and Commercial	Oil boilers to heat pumps in community centres	63	205
Public and Commercial	Warm air blowers in industrial buildings/warehouses	60	288
Public and Commercial	High efficiency boilers in retail buildings	60	-116
Public and Commercial	High efficiency boilers in industrial buildings/warehouses	60	-69
Public and Commercial	LED lighting upgrades in office buildings	56	1293

Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Carbon mitigated (kt CO ₂ e):	Cost per tonne (£):
Transport	Small diesel car journeys to electric train journeys	56	3054
Public and Commercial	Air tightness in industrial buildings/warehouses	53	229
Transport	Large diesel car journeys to electric train journeys	52	-1863
Transport	Medium diesel car journeys to electric train journeys	51	322
Domestic	Draught proofing in domestic buildings	51	-255
Public and Commercial	Oil boilers to heat pumps in healthcare buildings	46	354
Public and Commercial	Heating controls in industrial buildings/warehouses	46	36
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial PV installations in office buildings	44	1408
Domestic	Tank thermostats in domestic buildings	42	-273
Public and Commercial	Heating controls in office buildings	42	60
Public and Commercial	High efficiency boilers in office buildings	41	-58
Public and Commercial	Heating controls in retail buildings	38	80
Public and Commercial	Fabric improvements in retail buildings	37	4787
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial PV installations in retail buildings	35	2125
Public and Commercial	LED conversions in office buildings	35	-1049
Public and Commercial	Oil boilers to heat pumps in non-retail buildings	34	2422
Public and Commercial	External shading in office buildings	25	913
Public and Commercial	Heat recovery in office buildings	25	356
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial retrofits in non-retail buildings	25	892
Public and Commercial	Fan efficiency upgrades in retail buildings	23	-1287
Public and Commercial	LED in non-retail buildings	22	2019
Public and Commercial	New LED system in office buildings	21	-1133

Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Carbon mitigated (kt CO ₂ e):	Cost per tonne (£):
Public and Commercial	Oil boilers to heat pumps in hotels	21	354
Domestic	A++ rated cold appliances in domestic buildings	21	165
Domestic	Reduce heating for washing machines in domestic buildings	20	-1985
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial PV installations in non-retail buildings	19	2757
Public and Commercial	Daylight sensing lighting upgrades in office buildings	19	-929
Public and Commercial	LED conversions in non-retail buildings	19	-378
Domestic	Thermostatic radiator valves in domestic buildings	19	90
Public and Commercial	Water-cooling beams in office buildings	16	2092
Public and Commercial	LED conversions in retail buildings	14	2172
Public and Commercial	Heat recovery in non-retail buildings	14	628
Domestic	District heating networks in domestic buildings	14	-811
Public and Commercial	Oil boilers to heat pumps in education buildings	13	1763
Public and Commercial	Highly-efficient air cooling system in retail buildings	12	-1336
Public and Commercial	95% efficiency boilers in non-retail buildings	11	59
Transport	Small diesel car journeys to electric bus journeys	11	446
Transport	Large diesel car journeys to electric bus journeys	10	58
Public and Commercial	New LED system in industrial buildings/warehouses	10	2372
Transport	Medium diesel car journeys to electric bus journeys	10	254
Public and Commercial	LED conversions in industrial buildings/warehouses	10	2256
Public and Commercial	Solar thermal in retail buildings	9	1377
Public and Commercial	Electrical circuitry efficiency upgrades in retail buildings	9	-1430
Public and Commercial	Solar thermal in office buildings	9	1694
Public and Commercial	LED conversions in office buildings	9	-1049

Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Carbon mitigated (kt CO ₂ e):	Cost per tonne (£):
Public and Commercial	LED lighting upgrades in education buildings	9	1211
Public and Commercial	LED in community centres	8	2316
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial retrofits in healthcare buildings	7	838
Public and Commercial	Air-cooling beams in office buildings	7	5508
Public and Commercial	Water-cooling beams in non-retail buildings	7	2237
Public and Commercial	New LED system in non-retail buildings	7	-891
Public and Commercial	New LED system in retail buildings	7	2458
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial retrofits in community centres	7	935
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial retrofits in education buildings	6	570
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial PV installations in healthcare buildings	6	2177
Public and Commercial	Heating controls in non-retail buildings	6	454
Public and Commercial	LED lighting upgrades in healthcare buildings	6	1891
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial PV installations in community centres	5	2911
Public and Commercial	LED conversions in healthcare buildings	5	-258
Public and Commercial	LED lighting upgrades in hotels	5	2419
Public and Commercial	Movement sensing lighting upgrades in industrial buildings/warehouses	4	6364
Public and Commercial	Solar thermal in non-retail buildings	4	1803
Public and Commercial	Electrical circuitry efficiency upgrades in office buildings	4	-1371
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial PV installations in education buildings	4	2677
Public and Commercial	Air-cooling beams in non-retail buildings	4	4734
Public and Commercial	AC upgrades in retail buildings	4	-1302

Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Carbon mitigated (kt CO2e):	Cost per tonne (£):
Public and Commercial	Movement sensing lighting upgrades in retail buildings	4	7314
Public and Commercial	LED conversions in community centres	4	-511
Public and Commercial	Electrical circuitry efficiency upgrades in industrial buildings/warehouses	4	-1012
Public and Commercial	Heat recovery in community centres	3	467
Public and Commercial	95% efficiency boilers in healthcare buildings	3	81
Public and Commercial	Movement sensing lighting upgrades in office buildings	3	4977
Public and Commercial	Heat recovery in healthcare buildings	3	494
Public and Commercial	95% efficiency boilers in community centres	3	94
Public and Commercial	AC upgrades in office buildings	3	-1377
Public and Commercial	Heat recovery in education buildings	3	656
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial retrofits in hotels	3	1038
Domestic	Turn unnecessary lighting off in domestic buildings	3	-1985
Public and Commercial	AC upgrades in non-retail buildings	3	-1383
Public and Commercial	95% efficiency boilers in education buildings	3	65
Public and Commercial	LED conversions in education buildings	3	-457
Public and Commercial	High efficiency AC system in retail buildings	3	-1106
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial PV installations in hotels	3	2509
Public and Commercial	Daylight sensing lighting upgrades in non-retail buildings	2	-239
Public and Commercial	New LED system in healthcare buildings	2	-1074
Public and Commercial	New LED system in community centres	2	-1037
Public and Commercial	Water-cooling beams in healthcare buildings	2	2177

Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Carbon mitigated (kt CO2e):	Cost per tonne (£):
Public and Commercial	Fan efficiency upgrades in office buildings	2	-741
Public and Commercial	Heat recovery in hotels	2	592
Public and Commercial	Highly-efficient air cooling system in office buildings	2	-1219
Public and Commercial	Heating controls in healthcare buildings	2	507
Public and Commercial	Heating controls in community centres	2	324
Public and Commercial	Water-cooling beams in community centres	2	2238
Public and Commercial	95% efficiency boilers in hotels	2	28
Public and Commercial	Water-cooling beams in education buildings	2	2208
Public and Commercial	New LED system in education buildings	2	-1038
Public and Commercial	Heating controls in education buildings	1	437
Transport	Small diesel car journeys to diesel train journeys	1	7775
Transport	Large diesel car journeys to diesel train journeys	1	3000
Transport	Medium diesel car journeys to diesel train journeys	1	6307
Public and Commercial	Solar thermal in healthcare buildings	1	1813
Public and Commercial	External shading in non-retail buildings	1	70
Public and Commercial	Air-cooling beams in healthcare buildings	1	4504
Public and Commercial	Air-cooling beams in education buildings	1	4303
Public and Commercial	Water-cooling beams in hotels	1	1988
Public and Commercial	Air-cooling beams in community centres	1	5396
Public and Commercial	Solar thermal in community centres	1	1763
Public and Commercial	Daylight sensing lighting upgrades in healthcare buildings	1	-167
Public and Commercial	High efficiency AC system in non-retail buildings	1	-882

Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Carbon mitigated (kt CO2e):	Cost per tonne (£):
Public and Commercial	High efficiency AC system in office buildings	1	-878
Public and Commercial	New LED system in hotels	1	-958
Public and Commercial	LED conversions in hotels	1	-227
Public and Commercial	Solar thermal in education buildings	1	1625
Public and Commercial	Daylight sensing lighting upgrades in education buildings	1	-197
Public and Commercial	AC upgrades in healthcare buildings	1	-1404
Public and Commercial	Daylight sensing in community centres	1	-300
Public and Commercial	External shading in healthcare buildings	1	189
Public and Commercial	External shading in community centres	1	283
Public and Commercial	AC upgrades in education buildings	1	-1394
Public and Commercial	External shading in education buildings	1	-150
Public and Commercial	Highly-efficient air cooling system in non-retail buildings	0.5	-835
Public and Commercial	AC upgrades in hotels	0.5	-1393
Public and Commercial	Heating controls in hotels	0.5	552
Public and Commercial	Fan efficiency upgrades in non-retail buildings	0.5	751
Public and Commercial	External shading in hotels	0.5	67
Public and Commercial	AC upgrades in community centres	0.4	-1407
Public and Commercial	Air-cooling beams in hotels	0.4	4635
Public and Commercial	Movement sensing lighting upgrades in non-retail buildings	0.3	27620
Public and Commercial	Solar thermal in hotels	0.3	1834
Public and Commercial	AC upgrades in industrial buildings/warehouses	0.2	-720

Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Carbon mitigated (kt CO2e):	Cost per tonne (£):
Public and Commercial	Daylight sensing lighting upgrades in hotels	0.2	-120
Public and Commercial	High efficiency AC system in healthcare buildings	0.2	-894
Public and Commercial	Fan efficiency upgrades in healthcare buildings	0.2	942
Public and Commercial	High efficiency AC system in community centres	0.2	-1014
Public and Commercial	Highly-efficient air cooling system in community centres	0.2	-832
Public and Commercial	Fan efficiency upgrades in education buildings	0.1	851
Public and Commercial	High efficiency AC system in education buildings	0.1	-935
Public and Commercial	Fan efficiency upgrades in community centres	0.1	1311
Public and Commercial	Highly-efficient air cooling system in healthcare buildings	0.1	-805
Public and Commercial	High efficiency AC system in hotels	0.1	-936
Public and Commercial	Movement sensing lighting upgrades in healthcare buildings	0.1	32664
Public and Commercial	Movement sensing lighting upgrades in education buildings	0.1	28144
Public and Commercial	Movement sensing lighting upgrades in community centres	0.1	24734
Public and Commercial	Fan efficiency upgrades in hotels	0.1	842
Public and Commercial	Highly-efficient air cooling system in education buildings	0.05	-895
Public and Commercial	Highly-efficient air cooling system in hotels	0.04	-815
Public and Commercial	Movement sensing lighting upgrades in hotels	0.03	30236

Appendix 6 – Belfast Region’s league table of most cost-effective options

Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Cost per tonne (£)	Carbon mitigated (kt CO ₂ e):
Domestic	A rated ovens in domestic buildings	-2975	3
Domestic	Reduce heating for washing machines in domestic buildings	-1985	20
Domestic	Turn unnecessary lighting off in domestic buildings	-1985	3
Transport	Large diesel car journeys to electric train journeys	-1863	52
Transport	Large petrol car journeys to electric bus journeys	-1830	0
Domestic	Integrated digital TVs in domestic buildings	-1820	-5
Domestic	A+ rated wet appliances in domestic buildings	-1758	4
Transport	Medium petrol car journeys to electric bus journeys	-1678	0
Domestic	Induction hobs in domestic buildings	-1620	1
Transport	Small petrol car journeys to electric bus journeys	-1527	0
Public and Commercial	Electrical circuitry efficiency upgrades in retail buildings	-1430	9
Public and Commercial	AC upgrades in community centres	-1407	0
Public and Commercial	AC upgrades in healthcare buildings	-1404	1
Public and Commercial	AC upgrades in education buildings	-1394	1
Public and Commercial	AC upgrades in hotels	-1393	0
Public and Commercial	AC upgrades in non-retail buildings	-1383	3
Public and Commercial	AC upgrades in office buildings	-1377	3
Public and Commercial	Electrical circuitry efficiency upgrades in office buildings	-1371	4
Public and Commercial	Highly-efficient air cooling system in retail buildings	-1336	12
Public and Commercial	AC upgrades in retail buildings	-1302	4
Public and Commercial	Fan efficiency upgrades in retail buildings	-1287	23
Domestic	Low energy lighting in domestic buildings	-1250	104
Public and Commercial	Highly-efficient air cooling system in office buildings	-1219	2
Transport	Large petrol car journeys to diesel bus journeys	-1191	0

Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Cost per tonne (£)	Carbon mitigated (kt CO ₂ e):
Public and Commercial	New LED system in office buildings	-1133	21
Public and Commercial	High efficiency AC system in retail buildings	-1106	3
Public and Commercial	New LED system in healthcare buildings	-1074	2
Transport	Medium petrol car journeys to diesel bus journeys	-1063	0
Public and Commercial	LED conversions in office buildings	-1049	35
Public and Commercial	New LED system in education buildings	-1038	2
Public and Commercial	New LED system in community centres	-1037	2
Public and Commercial	High efficiency AC system in community centres	-1014	0
Public and Commercial	Electrical circuitry efficiency upgrades in industrial buildings/warehouses	-1012	4
Public and Commercial	New LED system in hotels	-958	1
Public and Commercial	High efficiency AC system in hotels	-936	0
Public and Commercial	High efficiency AC system in education buildings	-935	0
Public and Commercial	Daylight sensing lighting upgrades in office buildings	-929	19
Public and Commercial	Highly-efficient air cooling system in education buildings	-895	0
Public and Commercial	High efficiency AC system in healthcare buildings	-894	0
Public and Commercial	New LED system in non-retail buildings	-891	7
Public and Commercial	High efficiency AC system in non-retail buildings	-882	1
Public and Commercial	High efficiency AC system in office buildings	-878	1
Public and Commercial	Highly-efficient air cooling system in non-retail buildings	-835	0
Public and Commercial	Highly-efficient air cooling system in community centres	-832	0
Public and Commercial	Highly-efficient air cooling system in hotels	-815	0
Domestic	District heating networks in domestic buildings	-811	14

Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Cost per tonne (£)	Carbon mitigated (kt CO ₂ e):
Public and Commercial	Highly-efficient air cooling system in healthcare buildings	-805	0
Public and Commercial	Fan efficiency upgrades in office buildings	-741	2
Public and Commercial	AC upgrades in industrial buildings/warehouses	-720	0
Transport	Small petrol car journeys to diesel bus journeys	-669	0
Transport	Medium diesel car journeys to bicycle journeys	-617	260
Transport	Medium diesel car journeys to walking journeys	-608	285
Transport	Medium petrol car journeys to walking journeys	-594	0
Transport	Small diesel car journeys to walking journeys	-592	311
Transport	Small diesel car journeys to bicycle journeys	-588	284
Transport	Small petrol car journeys to walking journeys	-580	0
Transport	Large diesel car journeys to bicycle journeys	-578	265
Transport	Large diesel car journeys to walking journeys	-557	290
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial retrofits in office buildings	-550	108
Public and Commercial	LED conversions in office buildings	-549	35
Transport	Large petrol car journeys to walking journeys	-548	0
Domestic	Tank insulation in domestic buildings	-548	70
Transport	Medium petrol car journeys to bicycle journeys	-545	0
Transport	Large diesel car journeys to diesel bus journeys	-536	0
Transport	Small petrol car journeys to bicycle journeys	-521	0
Transport	Large petrol car journeys to bicycle journeys	-513	0
Public and Commercial	LED conversions in community centres	-511	4
Domestic	Biomass boilers in domestic buildings	-486	7
Public and Commercial	LED conversions in education buildings	-457	3
Domestic	Loft insulation in domestic buildings	-431	1713
Public and Commercial	LED conversions in non-retail buildings	-378	19
Domestic	Lowering thermostats in domestic buildings	-345	136
Domestic	Reduce household heating by 1 C in domestic buildings	-319	781
Public and Commercial	Daylight sensing in community centres	-300	1
Domestic	Cavity wall insulation in domestic buildings	-300	952

Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Cost per tonne (£)	Carbon mitigated (kt CO2e):
Domestic	Top-up loft insulation in domestic buildings	-291	221
Public and Commercial	Heat recovery in retail buildings	-279	144
Domestic	Tank thermostats in domestic buildings	-273	42
Public and Commercial	LED conversions in healthcare buildings	-258	5
Domestic	Draught proofing in domestic buildings	-255	51
Transport	Medium diesel car journeys to EV journeys	-244	309
Transport	Medium petrol car journeys to EV journeys	-242	316
Public and Commercial	Daylight sensing lighting upgrades in non-retail buildings	-239	2
Transport	Large diesel car journeys to EV journeys	-233	314
Transport	Large petrol car journeys to EV journeys	-232	321
Public and Commercial	LED conversions in hotels	-227	1
Domestic	Floor insulation in domestic buildings	-220	408
Transport	Small diesel car journeys to EV journeys	-215	337
Transport	Small petrol car journeys to EV journeys	-214	345
Public and Commercial	Daylight sensing lighting upgrades in education buildings	-197	1
Public and Commercial	Daylight sensing lighting upgrades in healthcare buildings	-167	1
Public and Commercial	External shading in education buildings	-150	1
Transport	Diesel bus journeys to electric bus journeys	-146	286
Public and Commercial	Air tightness in office buildings	-126	103
Transport	Diesel light goods vehicles to electric light goods vehicles	-124	1467
Public and Commercial	Daylight sensing lighting upgrades in hotels	-120	0
Public and Commercial	Air tightness in retail buildings	-120	765
Public and Commercial	High efficiency boilers in retail buildings	-116	60
Public and Commercial	Fabric improvements in industrial buildings/warehouses	-81	2019
Public and Commercial	High efficiency boilers in industrial buildings/warehouses	-69	60
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial retrofits in industrial buildings/warehouses	-61	261

Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Cost per tonne (£)	Carbon mitigated (kt CO2e):
Public and Commercial	High efficiency boilers in office buildings	-58	41
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial retrofits in retail buildings	-55	355
Transport	Large petrol car journeys to electric train journeys	-27	0
Transport	Diesel light ordinary goods vehicle to electric ordinary goods vehicle	-8	2351
Domestic	Internal wall insulation in domestic buildings	-7	693
Transport	Diesel heavy ordinary goods vehicle to electric ordinary goods vehicle	-2	2140
Land-use	Optimal pH lining	-2	436
Land-use	Manure spreading on farmland	-1	684
Land-use	Low tilling practices	0	195
Land-use	Miscanthus planting	13	2215
Land-use	Afforestation of grazing land	14	45480
Land-use	Cover crops	17	792
Land-use	Wetlands - Medium ambition restoration	19	2651
Land-use	Wetlands - High ambition restoration	24	3556
Public and Commercial	95% efficiency boilers in hotels	28	2
Land-use	Wetlands - Low ambition restoration	32	1094
Public and Commercial	Heating controls in industrial buildings/warehouses	36	46
Land-use	Methane inhibitors in animal feed for dairy cows	36	1761
Land-use	Methane inhibitors in animal feed for beef cows	54	904
Transport	Large diesel car journeys to electric bus journeys	58	10
Public and Commercial	95% efficiency boilers in non-retail buildings	59	11
Public and Commercial	Heating controls in office buildings	60	42
Public and Commercial	95% efficiency boilers in education buildings	65	3
Public and Commercial	External shading in hotels	67	0
Public and Commercial	External shading in non-retail buildings	70	1
Public and Commercial	Heating controls in retail buildings	80	38
Public and Commercial	95% efficiency boilers in healthcare buildings	81	3

Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Cost per tonne (£)	Carbon mitigated (kt CO ₂ e):
Land-use	Silvopastoral agroforestry	87	817
Domestic	Thermostatic radiator valves in domestic buildings	90	19
Public and Commercial	95% efficiency boilers in community centres	94	3
Transport	Medium petrol car journeys to electric train journeys	97	0
Industry	Compressors and variable speed systems in industry	138	437
Industry	Compressed air systems in industry	141	568
Domestic	Oil boilers to heat pumps in domestic buildings	144	9378
Industry	Fan correction, repairs, and upgrades in industry	149	605
Industry	Pump upgrades, repairs and maintenance in industry	155	848
Land-use	Silvoarable agroforestry	156	200
Land-use	Hedgerow expansion	157	331
Domestic	External wall insulation in domestic buildings	159	1228
Domestic	A++ rated cold appliances in domestic buildings	165	21
Public and Commercial	External shading in healthcare buildings	189	1
Public and Commercial	Oil boilers to heat pumps in community centres	205	63
Transport	Small petrol car journeys to electric train journeys	228	0
Public and Commercial	Air tightness in industrial buildings/warehouses	229	53
Land-use	Nitrate supplements in animal feed for pigs	232	204
Transport	Medium diesel car journeys to electric bus journeys	254	10
Domestic	Gas combi-boilers in domestic buildings	277	726
Land-use	Nitrate supplements in animal feed for sheep	278	1087
Public and Commercial	External shading in community centres	283	1
Public and Commercial	Warm air blowers in industrial buildings/warehouses	288	60
Transport	Medium diesel car journeys to electric train journeys	322	51
Public and Commercial	Heating controls in community centres	324	2
Industry	Condensing and insulation measures to boilers and steam piping in industry	339	2870
Domestic	Solar PV in domestic buildings	345	2011
Industry	Refrigeration efficiency and technical upgrades in industry	350	182
Industry	Improving efficiency of boilers and steam piping in industry	353	1962

Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Cost per tonne (£)	Carbon mitigated (kt CO ₂ e):
Public and Commercial	Oil boilers to heat pumps in healthcare buildings	354	46
Public and Commercial	Oil boilers to heat pumps in hotels	354	21
Public and Commercial	Heat recovery in office buildings	356	25
Industry	Furnace efficiency and heat recovery mechanisms in industry	363	360
Public and Commercial	Heating controls in education buildings	437	1
Public and Commercial	Oil boilers to heat pumps in retail buildings	441	416
Transport	Small diesel car journeys to electric bus journeys	446	11
Public and Commercial	Heating controls in non-retail buildings	454	6
Public and Commercial	Replace single with double glazing in office buildings	456	191
Public and Commercial	Heat recovery in community centres	467	3
Domestic	Whole house retrofits in domestic buildings	488	5778
Public and Commercial	Heat recovery in healthcare buildings	494	3
Public and Commercial	Heating controls in healthcare buildings	507	2
Public and Commercial	Heating controls in hotels	552	0
Transport	Medium diesel car journeys to diesel bus journeys	567	0
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial retrofits in education buildings	570	6
Public and Commercial	Heat recovery in hotels	592	2
Public and Commercial	Heat recovery in non-retail buildings	628	14
Public and Commercial	Heat recovery in education buildings	656	3
Public and Commercial	Fan efficiency upgrades in non-retail buildings	751	0
Domestic	Heat pumps in domestic buildings	753	1128
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial retrofits in healthcare buildings	838	7
Public and Commercial	Fan efficiency upgrades in hotels	842	0

Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Cost per tonne (£)	Carbon mitigated (kt CO2e):
Public and Commercial	Fan efficiency upgrades in education buildings	851	0
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial retrofits in non-retail buildings	892	25
Public and Commercial	External shading in office buildings	913	25
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial retrofits in community centres	935	7
Public and Commercial	Fan efficiency upgrades in healthcare buildings	942	0
Public and Commercial	Oil boilers to heat pumps in office buildings	945	295
Transport	Small diesel car journeys to diesel bus journeys	954	0
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial retrofits in hotels	1038	3
Public and Commercial	LED lighting upgrades in education buildings	1211	9
Domestic	Solar thermal in domestic buildings	1287	110
Public and Commercial	LED lighting upgrades in office buildings	1293	56
Public and Commercial	Fan efficiency upgrades in community centres	1311	0
Public and Commercial	Solar thermal in retail buildings	1377	9
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial PV installations in office buildings	1408	-
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial PV installations in industrial buildings/warehouses	1497	110
Public and Commercial	Solar thermal in education buildings	1625	1
Public and Commercial	Solar thermal in office buildings	1694	9
Public and Commercial	Solar thermal in community centres	1763	1
Public and Commercial	Oil boilers to heat pumps in education buildings	1763	13
Public and Commercial	Solar thermal in non-retail buildings	1803	4
Public and Commercial	Solar thermal in healthcare buildings	1813	1
Public and Commercial	Solar thermal in hotels	1834	0

Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Cost per tonne (£)	Carbon mitigated (kt CO2e):
Public and Commercial	LED lighting upgrades in healthcare buildings	1891	6
Public and Commercial	Water-cooling beams in hotels	1988	1
Public and Commercial	LED in non-retail buildings	2019	22
Public and Commercial	Water-cooling beams in office buildings	2092	16
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial PV installations in retail buildings	2125	-
Public and Commercial	LED conversions in retail buildings	2172	14
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial PV installations in healthcare buildings	2177	6
Public and Commercial	Water-cooling beams in healthcare buildings	2177	2
Domestic	Triple glazing in domestic buildings	2188	217
Public and Commercial	Water-cooling beams in education buildings	2208	2
Public and Commercial	Water-cooling beams in non-retail buildings	2237	7
Public and Commercial	Water-cooling beams in community centres	2238	2
Public and Commercial	LED conversions in industrial buildings/warehouses	2256	10
Public and Commercial	LED in community centres	2316	8
Public and Commercial	New LED system in industrial buildings/warehouses	2372	10
Public and Commercial	LED lighting upgrades in hotels	2419	5
Public and Commercial	Oil boilers to heat pumps in non-retail buildings	2422	34
Public and Commercial	New LED system in retail buildings	2458	7
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial PV installations in hotels	2509	3
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial PV installations in education buildings	2677	4
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial PV installations in non-retail buildings	2757	19

Sector	Low Carbon Measure:	Cost per tonne (£)	Carbon mitigated (kt CO2e):
Public and Commercial	Area-based commercial PV installations in community centres	2911	5
Transport	Large diesel car journeys to diesel train journeys	3000	1
Transport	Small diesel car journeys to electric train journeys	3054	56
Transport	Large petrol car journeys to diesel train journeys	3366	0
Domestic	Passivehaus standards in new domestic buildings	3462	174
Public and Commercial	Air-cooling beams in education buildings	4303	1
Public and Commercial	Air-cooling beams in healthcare buildings	4504	1
Public and Commercial	Air-cooling beams in hotels	4635	0
Public and Commercial	Air-cooling beams in non-retail buildings	4734	4
Public and Commercial	Fabric improvements in retail buildings	4787	37
Public and Commercial	Movement sensing lighting upgrades in office buildings	4977	3
Transport	Medium petrol car journeys to diesel train journeys	4996	0
Public and Commercial	Air-cooling beams in community centres	5396	1
Public and Commercial	Air-cooling beams in office buildings	5508	7
Domestic	Reduced standby consumption in domestic buildings	6043	-
Transport	Small petrol car journeys to diesel train journeys	6236	0
Transport	Medium diesel car journeys to diesel train journeys	6307	1
Public and Commercial	Movement sensing lighting upgrades in industrial buildings/warehouses	6364	4
Public and Commercial	Movement sensing lighting upgrades in retail buildings	7314	4
Transport	Small diesel car journeys to diesel train journeys	7775	1
Public and Commercial	Movement sensing lighting upgrades in community centres	24734	0
Public and Commercial	Movement sensing lighting upgrades in non-retail buildings	27620	0
Public and Commercial	Movement sensing lighting upgrades in education buildings	28144	0
Public and Commercial	Movement sensing lighting upgrades in hotels	30236	0
Public and Commercial	Movement sensing lighting upgrades in healthcare buildings	32664	0

Appendix 7 – Local authority data sources and case study references

Sector	Description	Source
Development plans	Ards and North Down Local Development Planning	https://www.ardsandnorthdown.gov.uk/resident/planning/local-development-plan
Development plans	Ards and North Down Sustainability Planning	https://www.dashdigital.com/aandbc/roadmap_to_sustainability/MobilePagedReplica.action?pm=1&folio=1#pg1
Development plans	Industrial and Economic Land Monitor 2022	https://www.midandeastantrim.gov.uk/business/planning/local-development-plan/industrial-and-economic-land-monitor-2018
Development plans	Retail and Commercial Leisure Need and Capacity Study	https://issuu.com/meabc/docs/dps-127_technical_supplement_6_appendix_d_retail_a
Commercial	Commercial floorspace breakdowns by local authority	Land and Property Services
Domestic	Environmental Performance Certificates	Department of Finance, NI
Commercial	Environmental Performance Certificates	Department of Finance, NI
Local authority	Antrim and Newtownabbey climate action information	https://antrimandnewtownabbey.gov.uk/council/climate-change/
Local authority	Belfast city climate action information	https://www.belfastcity.gov.uk/documents/belfast-resilience-ambitions-a-climate-plan-for-be
Local authority	Belfast city climate action information	https://www.belfastclimate.org.uk

Local authority	Belfast city climate action information	https://pcancities.org.uk/sites/default/files/Belfast%20Net-Zero%20Carbon%20Roadmap_0.pdf
Local authority	Lisburn and Castlereagh Biodiversity Plan	https://www.lisburncastlereagh.gov.uk/things-to-do/parks-and-open-spaces/biodiversity
Local authority	Lisburn and Castlereagh Local Development Plan	https://www.lisburncastlereagh.gov.uk/resident/planning/local-development-plan
Development plans	Mid and East Antrim Local Development Plan	https://www.midandeastantrim.gov.uk/business/planning/local-development-plan
Local authority	Mid and East Antrim current policies	https://www.midandeastantrim.gov.uk/business/planning/local-development-plan/current-plans-policies
Local authority	Mid and East Antrim environmental reports	https://www.midandeastantrim.gov.uk/council/policies-and-documents/climate-change-sustainability/climate-sustainability-environment-reporting
Transport	Newry, Mourne and Down Active Travel Masterplan	https://www.newrymouredown.org/media/uploads/nmd_active_travel_masterplan.pdf
Land-Use	Forests for Our Future – DAERA	https://www.daera-ni.gov.uk/news/forests-our-future-woodland-grant-schemes-reopen
Domestic	Retrofit Scheme – Newry, Mourne and Down	https://carboncopy.eco/initiatives/social-housing-retrofit-pilot-scheme
Transport	Belfast Metropolitan Area Transport Plan	https://www.infrastructure-ni.gov.uk/publications/belfast-metropolitan-transport-plan
Development plans	Belfast Local Development Plan	https://www.belfastcity.gov.uk/getmedia/78a2974f-05c3-40a3-bfe3-99e164c1116e/POP022_TP-Tra.pdf
Development Plans	Local Authority Planning, Area Information and Development Plans	https://www.infrastructure-ni.gov.uk/topics/planning/departmental-development-plans

Land-Use	Belfast Green and Blue Infrastructure Plan	https://www.pacni.gov.uk/sites/pacni/files/media-files/BCC-AD-GBIP_0.pdf
Development plans, Land-Use, Buildings	Antrim and Newtownabbey Local Development Planning Info	https://antrimandnewtownabbey.gov.uk/ldp/
Development plans, Land-Use	Newry, Mourne and Down Local Development Plan	https://www.newrymouredown.org/media/uploads/nmd_local_development_plan_2030_pop_medium_w_eb_version.pdf
Land-Use, Development Plans	Mid and East Antrim Rural Development Programme	https://www.midandeastantrim.gov.uk/business/amplify-mid-and-east-antrim/meardp
Development Plans	The Big Plan for Ards and North Down	https://www.ardsandnorthdown.gov.uk/resident/community-planning/the-big-plan-for-ards-and-north-down
Land-Use	Newry, Mourne and Down Local Biodiversity Action Plan	https://www.newrymouredown.org/media/uploads/LBAP.pdf
Land-Use	Newry, Mourne and Down Landscape Character Assessment	https://www.newrymouredown.org/media/uploads/ldp_paper_12_(part_1)_-countryside_-_landscape_character_asses(1).pdf
Land-Use	Antrim and Newtownabbey Landscape Character Assessment	https://antrimandnewtownabbey.gov.uk/getmedia/0f76af70-57b3-4db0-aabf-f2cc90dfbe73/Evidence-Paper-16-Landscape-Character-Assessment.pdf.aspx
Land-Use	Antrim and Newtownabbey Biodiversity Info	https://antrimandnewtownabbey.gov.uk/council/climate-change/biodiversity-(1)/
Land-Use	Ards and North Down Local Biodiversity Action Plan	https://www.ardsandnorthdown.gov.uk/images/assets/Local_Biodiversity_Action_Plan_2013-2017.pdf
Land-Use	Ards and North Down Rural Area Development Plan	https://www.ardsandnorthdown.gov.uk/downloads/Natural_Environment.pdf
Land-Use	Lisburn and Castlereagh Local Biodiversity Action Plan	https://www.lisburncastlereagh.gov.uk/uploads/planning/SUBDOC-078_Lisburn_Castlereagh_Local_Biodiversity_Action_Plan.pdf

Land-Use	Mid and East Antrim Local Biodiversity Action Plan	https://www.midandeantrim.gov.uk/downloads/LB-AP-DOC_FINAL_FOR_WEBSITE.pdf
Land-Use	Countryside Survey data	DAERA
Industry	NAEI industrial point source emissions data	https://naei.beis.gov.uk/data/mapping
Domestic Case Study 1	Leeds PIPES	https://www.local.gov.uk/case-studies/leeds-city-council-low-carbon-heat-network https://www.westyorks-ca.gov.uk/projects/clean-energy-and-environmental-resilience/leeds-pipes/ https://www.leeds-pipes.co.uk/
Domestic Case Study 2	Cosy Homes Oxfordshire	https://carboncopy.eco/initiatives/cosy-homes-oxfordshire https://cosyhomesoxfordshire.org/ https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/1024376/supply-chain-demonstrator-project-evaluation .pdf
Public and Commercial Case Study 1	Viking Energy Network Jarrow (VENJ)	https://carboncopy.eco/initiatives/viking-energy-network-jarrow https://www.southtyneside.gov.uk/article/3772/Overview#:~:text=Viking%20Energy%20Network%20Jarrow%20is,estimated%201%2C035%20tonnes%20per%20year
Public and Commercial Case Study 2	One Brighton	https://carboncopy.eco/initiatives/one-brighton https://www.bioregional.com/one-planet-living/one-planet-living-leaders/one-brighton-one-planet-living-leader http://www.cied.ac.uk/wordpress/wp-content/uploads/2018/04/LEHII-One-Brighton-Case-History_FINAL.pdf
Transport Case Study 1	Nottingham Workplace Parking Levy	https://www.nottinghamcity.gov.uk/wpl https://carboncopy.eco/initiatives/nottingham-workplace-parking-levy

FOR FURTHER INFORMATION:

Email: brcd@belfastcity.gov.uk

Tel: 028 9032 0202

Visit: belfastregioncitydeal.co.uk

Belfast
City Council

Antrim and
Newtownabbey
BOROUGH COUNCIL

Ards and
North Down
Borough Council

Lisburn &
Castlereagh
City Council

Mid & East
Antrim
Borough Council

Comhairle Ceantair
an Iúir, Mhúrn
agus an Dúin
Newry, Mourne
and Down
District Council

QUEEN'S
UNIVERSITY
BELFAST

Ulster
University

belfast
met

NORTHERN
Regional College

SERC
SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES

SRC
Southern
Regional
College

Northern Ireland
Executive

UK Government

 #BRCityDeal

 belfastregioncitydeal.co.uk